

OUTLINE

OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE

STRATEGIC PLAN FOR INTEGRATED INFRASTRUCTURE FOR OPEN SCIENCE PART 1

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English language version

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OBJECTIVE

The objective of the Strategic Plan for Integrated Open Science Infrastructure (SPII) is to develop a plan for a coherent, federated infrastructure that supports researchers and institutions in facilitating Open Science. The rationale is the lack of a common framework for an Open Science Infrastructure (OSI), which creates a risk of fragmentation. SPII aims to develop a broadly supported vision and target architecture that can guide and harmonise developments, so that a robust national Open Science Infrastructure can be realised step by step.

In this project, SPII Part 1 has been developed, consisting of a vision, a framework for the infrastructure and a fit-gap analysis of the current situation. Once SPII Part 1 is adopted, this can be further elaborated in SPII Parts 2 and 3.

SCOPE

The scope of SPII Part 1 can be summarised as follows:

- OSI (Open Science Infrastructure) is positioned as the Open Science perspective on the broader digital research infrastructure.
- A federated, modular design has been chosen as the starting point to align as closely as possible with existing systems.
- The focus of SPII Part 1 is on Research Data & Software Management, Open Scholarly Communication and Open Research Information, with an emphasis on generic functionalities for the FAIR sharing of research results, relevant to all disciplines.

VISION

The Open Science Infrastructure (OSI) ensures that Dutch research can be shared in a sustainable, FAIR and as openly as possible, and that the results can be archived, made visible and reused. The infrastructure also aggregates research information from various components and makes it as openly accessible as possible. The OSI operates flexibly and pragmatically through a federated, modular and integrated approach that safeguards the openness, digital sovereignty and digital sustainability of research results. Five main functions are distinguished::

- Sharing FAIR research results
- Increasing the visibility and dissemination of Dutch research results
- Monitoring usage via counters and metrics
- Open Research information from the various OSI components is consolidated and made available.
- Archiving and long-term preservation of Dutch research results.

DEVELOPMENT METHOD

When developing the proposals for OSI, the project group drew on the vision to design the federated structure as much as possible from the perspective of researchers and research support professionals. A number of key use cases have been developed for each domain (see Appendix A), with each one assessing whether, and if so, what the need is for federated components. Based on this, federated diagrams were developed, mapping out the desired federated solutions, the necessary federated agreements regarding interoperability, and the modules to be connected by the federation. Based on these federated diagrams, proposals were then developed for OSI components.

DESCRIPTION OF OSI COMPONENTS

- **Research administration and regulatory compliance:**
 - **Current situation:** Researchers are faced with increasing administrative obligations (DMP, ethics, GDPR, licences) at the start of a research project. Several institutions are currently developing a system to support researchers' workflows and avoid redundant data entry.
 - **Objective:** To focus on end-to-end integration by harmonising the data relevant to Open Science recorded in this process and utilising it during the implementation and completion of the research project. This will be achieved by 'incorporating' relevant metadata and automating processes where possible.
 - **Proposed solution:** Integration of Open Science-related metadata from the start of the project (such as DMP, ethics review) throughout the entire research process.
- **Optimisation and efficiency improvements to CRIS/repositories and their use as a publication channel:**
 - **Current situation:** Many institutions have set up an institutional repository and a CRIS system for registration and reporting purposes. This entails a considerable effort in terms of staff and resources. Working methods vary greatly between institutions and there is a significant amount of duplication of work.
 - **Objectives:**
 - Optimisation and efficiency improvements to the current CRIS systems and repositories.
 - Utilising these systems and efforts, designed for registration and reporting, in the publication process to support (innovative) forms of publication.
 - **Proposed solutions:** Linking the aforementioned systems via a federated solution and establishing a national publication aggregator for non-traditional research publications and innovative publication formats such as the PRC model. This national publication aggregator can also serve for archiving and long-term preservation, as well as acting as a starting point for making scientific information available to a wide audience.
- **Sharing and reusing (sensitive) research data infrastructure:**

- **Current situation:** The landscape of RDM infrastructure components is highly diverse and still evolving rapidly. With regard to Open Science aspects, there is little or no end-to-end integration: research administration → data management plan → data management environment → (long-term) data repository; and there is a lack of automated data access mechanisms for datasets with access restricted by conditions.
- **Objectives:**
 - End-to-end integration where possible through federation
 - Automation where possible to reduce the burden on researchers
- **Proposed solutions:**
 - Identifying the metadata developed during the various steps that is relevant to the sharing and reuse of the data and to the reproducibility of the research, so that it can be incorporated, reused and further supplemented during the research process.
 - Automation of data access mechanisms.
- **Sharing and reusing research software infrastructure:**
 - **Current situation:** With the implementation of the Research Software Directory several years ago, all the technical components are in place for the sharing and reuse of research software. However, adoption is lacking.
 - **Objectives:** To promote the adoption of sharing and reusing research software by developing widely supported Best Practices
 - **Proposed solutions:** Development of Best Practices where necessary.
- **Open research information, discovery and active dissemination:**
 - **Current situation:** A significant proportion of research information on Dutch research is not openly available. The information that is openly available is fragmented. Discovery and dissemination are facilitated by the Netherlands Research Portal, which still has gaps in its functionality.
 - **Objectives:**
 - An infrastructure for making open research information on Dutch research available, with the most comprehensive data collection possible, which can be used and analysed by all parties.
 - To improve the discovery and dissemination of Dutch research results, resulting in increased national and international visibility.
 - **Proposed solutions:**
 - The establishment of a metadata hub, where information about research and metrics is brought together with the aim of making it as openly available as possible.
 - The establishment of a discovery layer containing the same information as the metadata hub, presented in a manner suitable for discovery and active dissemination to various national and international search engines, aggregation platforms, etc.

DISCUSSION SPII PART 1, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR SPII PART 2

Stakeholder consultation: A limited consultation took place, which highlighted a need for broader involvement in a follow-up. In addition, the following were cited as the most important points of feedback:

- The detailed use cases mainly cover the start and completion of research and hardly, if at all, the implementation phase.
- Some infrastructural proposals (such as a national publication aggregator) have not yet been sufficiently discussed with stakeholders.
- Some advocate a more abstract, functional approach to OSI, independent of existing systems.

Conclusion: The responses to the consultation round show that there is considerable interest in a vision and strategy for Open Science infrastructure. This report can be seen as a first step and a catalyst for the further development of OSI.

Recommendations for SPII Part 2:

- We recommend splitting SPII Part 2 into Part 2 and Part 3.
- SPII 2 focuses on the technical implementation of SPII Part 1, with the following proposed deliverables:
 - Technical infrastructure elements, including a reference architecture, a metadata schema, and technical standards and agreements on interfaces
 - Proposal for a federated interoperability framework
 - A roadmap for OSI with development and implementation proposals for the period 2026–2029.

Once the deliverables of SPII Part 2 have been adopted, the organisational aspects can be developed in SPII Part 3 in close alignment with developments relating to EOSC-NL.

This report is a translation of the [Dutch version](#). It is basically a machine translation by DeepL, lightly edited afterwards. The translation has been made at the start of the SPII Part 2 which will communicate and report in English.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE

INTRODUCTION

An adequate national Open Science infrastructure (OSI) makes it easier and more appealing for researchers to apply Open Science in their research practice. Such infrastructure helps to comply with Open Science principles (e.g. FAIR research data and software) and the code of conduct on scientific integrity (e.g. traceability and transparency)¹. In addition, an adequate OSI can partially support researchers in complying with legislation and regulations (such as the GDPR) and institutional and organisational policies (regarding security, data management and ethics).

The principles for such an Open Science infrastructure were formulated at an earlier stage². The development of Open Science infrastructure is an important part of the *NPOS 2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda*³ and the UNL Open Science Agenda^{4,5}. The NPOS Ambition Document contains a number of objectives under the heading ‘*Make Open Science possible through Open Infrastructures*’, to which this report refers.

DEFINITION OF OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE

The project group has adopted the OSNL definition of Open Science Infrastructure:

OSI comprises tools, software, workflows, platforms and digital services required for the implementation of Open Science. OSI facilitates researchers in the management and sharing of research data, software, publications, hardware and other research outputs, such as tools, protocols and methods. OSI helps researchers to put Open Science into practice by enabling open access publishing and the sharing of data and software. In addition, OSI can contribute to the accessibility, discoverability and reuse of research output by the public and other parties outside academia, for example by increasing the societal impact of scientific knowledge. Finally, OSI can increase the transparency and reproducibility of scientific research, which contributes to the quality of the research and trust in science^a.

CURRENT SITUATION

The key developments are:

- Many universities and universities of applied sciences have already implemented parts of an Open Science infrastructure or are in the process of developing them.
- SURF has an innovation zone called ‘Strengthening Open Science’, within which infrastructure is also being strengthened or developed⁶.

^a Translated from English. See Call for proposals: Open Science Infrastructure, 2024, 1st OSNL

- A recent call for proposals by Open Science NL in this area yielded a large number of project proposals, demonstrating a significant need⁷.
- A pilot project has been launched for a Dutch EOSC node.

FRAMEWORK FOR OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE REQUIRED

The above shows that there are many initiatives regarding infrastructure for Open Science, for which a shared vision of the infrastructure for Open Science would be helpful. However, the alignment, coordination and prioritisation of existing infrastructure and the development of new infrastructure are proving difficult due to the lack of a general, widely supported framework for Open Science infrastructure. Such a common approach to OSI is also important from the perspective of cost control and the efficient use of resources for the research institutions involved. A common and widely supported framework, also known as a meta-plan, should be based on a general, widely supported vision of the integrated infrastructure for Open Science required by universities, universities of applied sciences and other knowledge institutions. This framework can then be used to identify the infrastructure components and describe the characteristics they should ideally meet^{1,6}. This idea has led to a project supported by the relevant stakeholders under the name *Strategic Plan for Integrated Infrastructure for Open Science (SPII)*. This report describes the results of SPII Part 1.

SPII IN TWO PARTS

The objectives for the final SPII are as follows:

- **Provides a vision of the integrated OSI with the desired modular components and interconnections:** The strategic plan contains an overview of the desired modular components of the Open Science infrastructure, including the characteristics they should ideally meet and the 'gap' compared to the infrastructure already available, as identified through fit/gap analyses. The plan also includes a description of the desired interconnections.
- **The identified gaps with the current infrastructure serve as a guideline for the replacement and/or (further) development** of existing or new infrastructure components and thus have a guiding and harmonising effect, ensuring that an adequate Open Science infrastructure is achieved step by step.
- **Will be periodically updated:** Given ongoing technical developments and changes in the availability of local, national and international components, the Open Science infrastructure is expected to require periodic updates. Given the lead time of the development plans, the aim is for the SPII for Open Science, to be delivered in 2025, to serve as a guide for development processes in the period 2026–2030, with an update required halfway through this period for the subsequent period.

The objective of SPII Part 1 is to formulate a vision for OSI that will enjoy broad support and to deliver an initial blueprint that convinces the various stakeholders of the value of such a strategic plan, thereby creating support for its further elaboration (provided for in SPII Part 2).

1.2 SCOPE OF SPII PART 1

1. Open Science infrastructure distinguished from research infrastructure:

- The aim is to develop an infrastructure plan for Open Science. In doing so, the distinction from digital research infrastructure (such as High Performance Computing, GWIs, etc.) is important. In other words: OSI is the Open Science perspective on (digital) research infrastructure. The connection to more discipline-oriented Open Science infrastructure components and to disciplinary research infrastructures is discussed in Part 2.

2. Federated infrastructure as a starting point:

- The basic principle is to base SPII as much as possible on existing systems. SPII therefore proposes a federated or federation-like structure for OSI, which is modular in design and integrated in approach. A reference architecture for OSI (similar to HOSA), which is yet to be developed, forms part of this structure.
- SPII Part 1 focuses on the technical design. The governance, organisation, resources and commitment required for a federated structure form part of the proposed SPII Part 3.

3. Research Data & Software Management (RDSM), Open Scholarly Communication infrastructure (OSC) and Open Research Information (ORI) infrastructure:

- SPII focuses on an OSI infrastructure for Research Data & Software Management, Open Scholarly Communication infrastructure and Open Research Information, and on the FAIR sharing of research results within these. SPII thereby expects to cover a significant part of the need for OSI.

4. Discipline-agnostic in Part 1:

- SPII Part 1 focuses on OSI functionalities relevant to Dutch research projects regardless of their discipline. The initial focus is on data that institutions can and wish to share effectively and efficiently through a federated infrastructure. The connection to more discipline-specific Open Science infrastructure components and to disciplinary research infrastructures is addressed in Part 2.

The scope is explained in more detail in Appendix B.

1.3 PROJECT DESIGN

Figure 1 Process steps and presentation in this report

This plan was developed by the SPII Part 1 project group – a small group of experts who were released by their institutions for a limited number of hours (100 hours) and a limited period (March–July 2025). In addition, the project group consisted of a project leader and an information architect, who were available for this purpose a few days a week during the aforementioned period.

In a first step, the project group developed a vision for OSI. This is presented in Chapter 2. In this vision, the FAIR sharing of research results was identified as the main function of OSI.

In a second step, work was carried out according to a method (use cases → federated diagrams → proposals for the OSI infrastructure; see 3.2 for a more detailed description).

In early June, the initial results were documented in version 0.7, which was subsequently discussed during a consultation round that included a number of sessions focused on the fit/gap analysis. Due to time constraints, only a limited number of stakeholders were consulted for this (see Appendix E for a full list of participants). This led to fit/gap analyses for each domain. In practice, these sessions focused mainly on the gaps, which is why the results are presented as gap analyses in Chapter 3.

Other feedback received from the consulted stakeholders has either been incorporated into the present version, or is presented in the discussion (see Chapter 4), or is presented in Appendix D with the suggestion that these be addressed in Part 2 where possible.

2. VISION FOR OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE

2.1 OVERVIEW OF OSI

Figure 2 Overview of Open Science Infrastructure (blue and green) and 5 intended main functions (orange)

Figure 2 presents a general outline of the Open Science Infrastructure, which is explained in more detail below.

2.2 VISION FOR THE OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE

The Open Science Infrastructure ensures that Dutch research can be shared sustainably and as openly as possible, and that the results can be reused, made visible and archived. The system also brings together research information from the various components and makes it available as openly as possible. OSI does this flexibly and pragmatically through a federated, modular and integrated approach that safeguards the openness and digital sovereignty of the knowledge institutions.

2.3 INTENDED FUNCTIONS OF OSI

2.3.1 SHARING OF FAIR RESEARCH RESULTS

OSI facilitates the sharing of FAIR research results from Dutch knowledge institutions. This involves the FAIR sharing of research results at the level of workflows of researchers and research support professionals.

Research results include, among other things:

- Publications, such as preprints, scientific articles, specialist and academic publications, conference proceedings, books and book chapters, theses, and monographs.
- Software, for example computer models, algorithms, software codes, descriptions, data and software packaged in *executables*.
- Data (sets), for example (descriptions of) research data, analysed data, databases, clinical trial data, synthetic data, collected data
- Models, for example prototypes, utensils, equipment developed or further developed for research or as a result of research.
- Protocols (research protocols, intervention protocols, instrumentation protocols), logbooks, lab journals.

The FAIR sharing of research results must be supported by a set of agreements:

- **Findable:** common PIDs (Persistent Identifiers), metadata standards
- **Accessible:** through common agreements on, among other things, access and rights management in accordance with the adage ‘Open where possible, closed where necessary’, use of common licences, etc.
- **Interoperable:** common metadata elements; common (often domain-specific) vocabularies/ontologies
- **Reusable:** common licences, common templates for contextual documentation, harmonisation of definitions, such as those relating to the sensitivity of datasets.

2.3.2 FUNCTIONS OF OSI AS A WHOLE

Visibility and dissemination of Dutch research results : This requires, amongst other things, rich metadata and the distribution of this metadata to (inter-)national aggregation platforms, search engines and databases/repositories.

Monitoring of usage : This is done by means of counters and metrics, which track the usage (and reviews) of the various components.

Open Research Information : Research information from the various components of the system is aggregated and made openly available. Users can retrieve this information, combine it with other datasets and analyse it. The analysing tools are not considered part of OSI.

Archiving and long-term preservation : This function aims to ensure the archiving and long-term preservation of research results. Archiving and preservation contribute to digital sovereignty.

2.3.3 PREREQUISITES

- **Digital sovereignty:** OSI aims to contribute to the digital sovereignty of knowledge institutions by (gradually) safeguarding core academic values, including data autonomy and the minimisation of vendor lock-ins. We propose adopting a pragmatic ‘ ’ approach towards commercial providers. When components from commercial providers are used within the OSI, the procurement process must apply criteria relating to public values to prevent vendor lock-in and safeguard data

autonomy^l, the use of open standards, and an exit strategy, so that the provider is replaceable (*substitutable providers*⁹) and the institutions can later switch to other (non-commercial) providers and (open-source) components without losing data.

- **Sustainability:** OSI must be designed to be sustainable. This means, amongst other things, that a number of financial preconditions must be met and a balanced funding model must be developed. This includes matters such as project funding exclusively for projects, structural national funding for core infrastructure components such as an interoperability layer and authentication services, possibly with a revenue model based on services, a reserve for operational costs covering approximately one year, and self-funding by institutions for, for example, local storage solutions and institution-specific infrastructure components^l. This is further elaborated in SPII Part 2. Another aspect of sustainability concerns the exit strategy, whereby it must be guaranteed that the data can be preserved and made accessible elsewhere in a sustainable manner and that the collection of that data can be continued by other means.
- **Compliant:** OSI must enable users – in addition to Open Science principles – to comply with legislation and regulations (e.g., GDPR), with institutional and organisational policies (such as rules regarding research data, ethics and security), and with the code of conduct for scientific integrity (transparency, traceability).
- **Data security:** Data security must be guaranteed in OSI by protecting datasets where necessary, by ensuring that data integrity is safeguarded and that there are safeguards against cybercrime.
- **Cost-effective:** Collaboration on and, where possible, integration of a shared OSI leads to cost control and the efficient use of resources. Collaboration is also a necessity: individual knowledge institutions are not expected to have sufficient resources to independently develop and maintain an OSI infrastructure.
- **Complementary, aligned and interoperable:** OSI is complementary, focuses on Open Science and aligns with existing, developed or developing infrastructures (both local, national and international), such as federated authentication (SURFconext), federated discovery via the Netherlands Research Portal, a number of project proposals submitted to OSNL for shared infrastructures, the DCC/Tier2 infrastructure currently under development, *large-scale research infrastructures* (e.g. GWIs, ERICs), and international infrastructures such as ORE, OpenAIRE and EOSC.

2.4 FOUR CHARACTERISTICS OF THE OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE

The OSI consists of: (a) institution-specific components; (b) components shared across multiple institutions; (c) national components; (d) international components; and (e) is based on (inter-)national standards and agreements on interoperability at four levels: technical, semantic, legal and organisational.

FEDERATED

- **Federation through common architectural agreements:** The components of the infrastructure are linked via structural, flexible, common architectural agreements with a view to achieving common functionality through interoperability.
- **Federation at national level:** For the Strategic Plan for Integrated Open Science Infrastructure (SPII), the federated structure is being developed at a supra-institutional, national level.

- **Connection to international infrastructures:** The federated structure ensures a coherent and functional technical infrastructure at national level, which can be connected to international infrastructures such as OpenAIRE, Open Research Europe and EOSC via interfaces.
- **Federated interoperability framework:**
 - Common agreements on standards and software for technical integration.
 - The federated infrastructure is also based on organisational aspects such as a system of agreements between institutions regarding rules on participation and access, data quality assurance, distribution of financial costs and governance^{11,12}.
- **Preservation of autonomy:** The federated model preserves the autonomy of the infrastructure components managed by the participating institutions, thereby promoting ownership and responsibility for them. However, it is essential that the architectural and federative agreements are consistently adhered to.

MODULAR

- **Modules at multiple levels:** The modules of the Open Science infrastructure may be modules of one or more institutions or may be situated at national or international level.
 - a) With institution-specific modules as the basis, the institutions retain control over the most important data held by each institution – the ‘data crown jewels’, such as data on researchers and research data. This source data is decoupled as much as possible from the application layer⁸. This allows the institutions to retain as much data autonomy as possible and scope for institution-specific policies. Examples include institutional CRIS systems and institutional repositories.
 - b) With components shared across multiple institutions, similar institutions can manage and develop modules, thereby achieving efficiency gains. Examples of components shared across multiple institutions include a Data Access Broker service or PubliNova.
 - c) The national modules and the shared connections to international infrastructures also offer efficiency benefits and/or insight into information about research results. The Netherlands Research Portal is an example.
- **Focus on connections between modules:** The focus of the Strategic Plan for Integrated Open Science Infrastructure (SPII) lies on the federated links between these modules and on the common agreements, rather than on the modules themselves.

INTEGRATED

- **Support for the Research Life Cycle:** The Open Science infrastructure is integrated because it aims to support multiple phases of the research life cycle. This means that the infrastructure is designed to provide support for Research Data and Software Management (RDSM), Open Scholarly Communication (OSC) and Open Research Information (ORI)^b.

^b This corresponds to two priorities of the NPOS Rolling Agenda: ‘Towards open scholarly communication’ and ‘Towards FAIR and open research outputs’.³

- **Integration is cost-effective:** Some components will be specific to one of these domains, whilst others will cover several. This integration makes the design, development and management more cost-effective and its use more secure.

OPEN

- **Open infrastructure:** The infrastructure is open where possible, and closed where necessary. This means that some (parts of) components will be accessible to a limited group due to management and/or security considerations.
- **Open connections:** The OSI is connected via open standards and/or APIs and follows international developments to define, expand or modernise open standards.
- **Open-source:** Where possible, the OSI's components utilise open-source software, open-source hardware and providers that respect data autonomy and do not involve 'vendor lock-in'. The aim is also to contribute to existing projects within open-source communities and to make any in-house software developments open-source.

2.5 OTHER CONSIDERATIONS

- **No rigid plan, but federated solutions:** SPII is not a rigid plan that prescribes exactly what must be implemented. Such plans are rarely implemented in practice. Instead, SPII aims to propose federated solutions to realise certain functions: this ensures that, in the event of implementation, the creativity of the developers and the latest technical developments are utilised to the full.
- **Added value:** The added value of the Open Science infrastructure naturally lies in facilitating and promoting Open Science for research at Dutch knowledge institutions. More specifically for the OSI itself, this means that its structure is organised around a number of functions which, due to their cross-institutional importance, simultaneously form the business case for it. The added value of a shared infrastructure for these functions lies in the cost-efficiency for the participating institutions and the promotion of collaboration between researchers across the participating institutions.
- **Flexibility in implementation:** The implementation of the OSI may follow different timelines for the various functions and for the different participants. The design also takes into account different levels of participation. Furthermore, the infrastructure must be designed in such a way that it can respond flexibly to new (technical) developments.
- **Agreements, governance and funding:** A federated technical system can only function if it is underpinned by a clear set of agreements. In this approach, the decision is made to first develop a design for the desired technical and semantic infrastructure and, in a subsequent step, to develop the associated agreements, governance and funding model that align as closely as possible with existing structures and models.
- **Flexibility regarding standards:** it is often not strictly necessary for a federated connection that the two systems use the same metadata standard, for example. It is possible to include a translation (crosswalk) in the API.

3. OUTLINE OF THE OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE

3.1 INFRASTRUCTURE CONTEXT

Figure3 OSI in context

OSI does not stand alone, but is embedded in the broader landscape of existing infrastructure that supports research. This includes, among other things, largely discipline-specific research infrastructure, but also the ecosystem of publishers, metadata providers, and so on. Figure 3 outlines this context.

Figure4 A more detailed breakdown of OSI

Zooming in on OSI, its components fall into a number of categories that support high-level functions, usually in combination (see Figure 4). Some examples:

- Visibility is facilitated by portals and monitors that provide information about Dutch research, including discovery platforms with search functionality and overlay journals that bundle curated collections of publications.
- Integrated research administration systems and research information systems (CRIS systems) work together to enable monitoring and reporting and to ensure compliance with regulations.

3.2 DEVELOPMENT OF THE OSI FRAMEWORK

Figure 5 Method for developing the OSI framework

The project group drew up 10 use cases of workflows for researchers and research support professionals. A large proportion of these use cases focus on the FAIR sharing of research results, the main function of OSI. This was done with a view to developing OSI as much as possible from the bottom up, from the perspective of researchers and research support professionals.

In summary, the method comprises the following steps:

1. For each use case, based on the steps in the workflow, the necessary technical elements were identified, along with which of these should be federated; the social and human elements that play a role in the workflow steps; and the federated agreements required regarding standards and interoperability.
2. For each domain, the federated solutions identified in the use cases are presented in a federated schema containing the list of federated agreements (technical, semantic, legal) and the modules to be connected by the federated solution.
3. The federated solutions as presented in the federated diagrams formed the basis for the proposals in the following section for the various components of the OSI infrastructure.

The use cases and federated diagrams are described in Appendix A.

3.3 OUTLINE OF OSI

Figure6 Outline of OSI

Figure 6 shows the outline of OSI in a block diagram. The description of the various interrelated blocks follows in the subsequent sections.

3.3.1 RESEARCH ADMINISTRATION AND REGULATORY COMPLIANCE

CURRENT SITUATION

- The administrative component of scientific research has grown significantly in scope and complexity in recent years. Researchers are faced with a growing number of obligations from research funders and institutions in the areas of research data management, ethical review, privacy legislation (such as the GDPR), data licences and contractual terms. Prior to commencing research, researchers

will often submit a grant application. This involves various document exchanges and communication workflows between the researcher, project control, research director, data steward, legal department, etc. In some cases, a DMP (data management plan) is also drawn up, reviewed and approved at this stage. These developments mean that research administration and regulatory compliance form an integral part of the research process. With regard to Open Science, at the start of a research project, these factors largely determine the extent to which the research process and the research results should be open, open under certain conditions, or closed. That is why the project group regards this as an important element of OSI.

- According to our information, several institutions (sometimes universities or universities of applied sciences, sometimes faculties within a university or university of applied sciences) are working on developing a system to, firstly, guide researchers' workflows and avoid duplicate data entry and, secondly, to take the first steps towards extending this metadata to the rest of the research project (including by incorporating it into CRIS systems).

WHAT WE AIM TO ACHIEVE

MAIN OBJECTIVE

Focusing on end-to-end integration by harmonising the data relevant to Open Science that is recorded in this process regarding research projects and utilising it during the implementation and completion of these projects. The latter is achieved by avoiding duplicate entries of the same data, by carrying forward relevant metadata during the implementation and completion of the research project, and by applying automation where possible.

SOME CONCRETE PROPOSALS

With regard to the information concerning the 'carrying forward' of Open Science information throughout the rest of the workflow, here are a few options for recording:

- Information from the DMP can be used to advise the researcher on suitable repositories and licences for publications, datasets and software.
- Information on open/restricted/closed can lead to the automatic setting of embargoes in the repository or automatic validation when the chosen conditions differ from the data in the research administration system.
- The metadata arising from the research administration process can be passed on and, where necessary, supplemented when archiving and publishing research outputs such as datasets, software or publications.

Regarding the research administration platforms that have been developed or are currently under development:

- The current situation is highly fragmented, whilst at the same time many institutions have not yet developed such a platform. This appears to be an opportunity to coordinate efforts, draw on *lessons learnt* and consider how best to structure this at a national level by developing a framework of agreements on Open Science aspects in the short term and pooling resources to apply these to the rest of the research process. In the longer term, this could lead to the development of a joint research administration system.
- The widespread implementation and linking of the persistent identifiers RAiD, Grant ID and ROR is an essential prerequisite for all of this.

GAP ANALYSIS

According to our information, initial steps have been taken across various institutions towards the development of a research administration platform to utilise metadata for the rest of the research process as well.

STAKEHOLDERS

Research offices at universities and faculties; developers of research administration systems, NWO, ZonMW and other research funders, staff involved in research such as data stewards.

RECOMMENDATION

Develop common agreements on the harmonisation of Open Science data and identify the technical possibilities for using these systems to feed Open Science aspects into the rest of the research process, drawing on the *lessons learnt* from the various research administration systems currently in use or under development at the different institutions.

3.3.2 CRIS/REPOSITORIES: OPTIMISATION AND EFFICIENCY IMPROVEMENTS AND USE AS A PUBLICATION CHANNEL

CURRENT SITUATION

- **Financial concerns and digital sovereignty:** There are concerns regarding the financial sustainability of the rising costs of Gold and Hybrid Open Access for journal articles with Dutch co-authors (approx. 53,000 per year, of which approx. 60% have a Dutch *corresponding* author). Dependence on a few major publishers in this regard also plays a role in terms of digital sovereignty.

- **Innovative publication formats:**

Partly prompted by the above concern, a search is underway for innovative Open Access publication formats:

- Much attention is being paid to Diamond OA journals, which currently account for a limited volume of approximately 4% of published articles.
 - The publication of preprints is also receiving greater attention (estimated at around 5,000 per year), partly in light of the decoupling of publication and peer review in the so-called PRC model. A variant of this is represented by, among others, Open Research Europe with *author-centred peer review*, whereby the author invites two peer reviewers themselves after the manuscript has been published.
 - For authors of non-traditional publications within the framework of Open Science – particularly at the start and during the conduct of the research – such as protocols, models, etc., there is currently no logical publication channel.
- **Institutional systems and working methods:** Many institutions have set up an institutional repository and a CRIS system. These are designed for registration and reporting purposes (such as the KUOZ reporting) and require a significant investment in terms of staff and resources. In practice, these systems are not, or hardly, coordinated with one another, and a great deal of duplication of effort occurs. The metadata from these systems is, however, aggregated in PubliNova (for universities of applied sciences) and at national level (NL Research Portal).

WHAT WE AIM TO ACHIEVE

MAIN OBJECTIVES

- A. Optimisation and efficiency improvements to the current CRIS/repository systems
 - B. Utilising these systems and efforts, which are designed for registration and reporting, in the publication process to support (innovative) forms of publication.
-

Relevant objective NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda

3.4 By 2030, there will be a public platform for scientific publications, enabling everyone in the Netherlands to reuse global scholarly output for their professional and societal engagement practices.

CONCRETE PROPOSALS

We have developed the two main objectives mentioned above into a number of concrete proposals that have been discussed within a limited circle. This has resulted in an additional proposal. It should be noted that these proposals require further discussion with a broader circle of relevant stakeholders.

1. Optimisation and efficiency improvements to the current CRIS/repository systems: This proposal involves a federation for the entry of publication objects and their metadata into the CRIS/repositories (efficiency and deduplication) and a version of the JISC Publication Router to automate the harvesting of full text as much as possible. This means, amongst other things, that outputs with multiple authors from different research institutions are exchanged between the repositories/CRIS systems in such a way that a single DOI is assigned, all authors are assigned ORCIDs, and only one institution provides metadata.

2A. Utilising the CRIS/repository infrastructure as a publication channel: In the process of output registration → institutional repository → aggregation, the focus of CRIS systems and institutional repositories lies on registration (retrospectively) and ensuring open access. With these infrastructure components, the institutions already handle part of the publication process that makes academic output discoverable. Particularly for output (such as reports) that does not go to publishers, this process is in fact already the step from internal document to public availability, as outlined above for research reports. In this process, some document types also already receive ‘institutional’ branding. This ‘publication function’ can be utilised much more effectively than is currently the case, in the following manner:

- The proposal is to set up an aggregator for publication objects originating from the CRIS/repositories of the various institutions and to use this as a publication channel for the benefit of authors: metadata enriched by the service organisations associated with CRIS/repositories (usually libraries) and the publication can be forwarded via a ‘publication channel’ to the relevant preprint server, Diamond or another journal via COAR’s Notify mechanism for an overlay journal. However, the publication object can also simply remain on the aggregator and, if desired, be commented on by readers via a post-publication review option. In principle, this could also be done from the repositories (i.e. without an aggregator), but this would require dozens of connections to be established, and the volume per repository is too low to be of interest for attracting significant ‘traffic’. The *composability* argument and the volume argument both argue in favour of a national platform. If this platform proves successful, it could be expanded to include, for example, entry points for SDGs, themes, etc.
- Other functions of the publication aggregator: (1) From the aggregator, harvesting for the KB’s eDepot can take place using a single connector. (2) The aggregator can serve as a starting point

to provide meaningful access to scientific information for the general public: one or more publication objects can be summarised in Dutch and/or layman's terms using AI tools.

- Feedback on this proposal focused primarily on the feasibility and added value of such a structure as a publication channel for researchers/authors, who might also perceive this as an infringement of academic freedom. In addition, version management of a publication in its various forms was seen as a difficulty, and the relationship between the institutional repository and the national platform was considered unclear.

2B. Institutional CRIS systems and a national repository: Following the discussion on the above proposal, several respondents from the consultation phase indicated that they did not favour an institutional repository and could well envisage a national repository being established to replace the institutional repositories. Metadata would then be provided by the CRIS systems, which would remain institutional. Such a national repository could in turn fulfil some of the functions mentioned above. Finally, possibilities were mentioned here for making such a platform suitable for Diamond OA journals, and reference was made to recent developments concerning Open Research Europe, which indicate that this platform will become open source in the near future and is also expected to gain additional functionalities.

Archiving and long-term preservation: The proposed aggregator for publications is also relevant for archiving and long-term preservation: the publications can be archived and preserved for the long term via a single connector with the KB's e-Depot. The URN:NBN resolver is also important in this regard.

Making content available to the general public: The proposed aggregator could also serve as a starting point for making research publications available in a way that is meaningful to the general public, for example through AI-generated translations into Dutch and/or non-academic language.

GAP ANALYSIS

- **Gap 1: Very different working methods and inclusion policies regarding the institutions' CRIS/repositories:** Some illustrations of these differences:
 - At one institution, researchers are asked to enter their publications themselves (researchers perceive this as a bureaucratic burden). Another institution, by contrast, takes the burden entirely off the researchers by retrieving metadata about their publications from various international sources (such as Scopus and Open Alex).
 - Many institutions do, however, have a defined, specific workflow for theses due to their PhD regulations.
 - This situation leads to different records being produced for the same publication. This occurs *between* institutions (a publication with authors from different universities or universities of applied sciences) and even sometimes *within* a single institution when different authors from the same institution enter their publications into the CRIS system.
- **Gap 2: There is a gap regarding non-traditional publication types:**
 - Several institutions indicated that they do not have an active inclusion policy for non-traditional publications ('We do nothing with grey literature').
 - Recognition and appreciation play an important role in this regard. Now that recognition and valuation of non-traditional publication types are gradually emerging, the

CRIS/repository systems should respond to this. In this context, it is noted that university medical centres are currently exploring the possibilities of recognising preprints (which meet certain quality criteria) as valid publications for a PhD thesis.

STAKEHOLDERS

Stakeholders include managers of CRIS/repository systems, authors of preprints and other non-traditional publications.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The proposal is to further develop the two steps listed below in SPII Part 2:

- CRIS/repository systems:
 - Synchronisation and harmonisation of working methods and inclusion policies
 - Federation of these systems with a view to efficiency and optimisation.
- Redesign of the infrastructure for publishing:
 - Further development of the possibilities of a national repository/publication aggregator/publication platform, particularly for non-traditional publications and innovative publication formats such as the PRC model.

3.3.3 INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SHARING AND REUSING (SENSITIVE) DATA

CURRENT SITUATION

We distinguish the following components:

- **Data management environments and working environments:** These are *workspaces* in which researchers from a research team can collect, edit and analyse their data. These environments also support the researchers' workflow and are linked to storage environments where the data is stored. SURF

Research Cloud^c and Yoda are examples of this.

- **Secure environment for data analysis of highly sensitive data:** a secure environment with *compute-to-data* functionality for highly sensitive data (e.g. SANE).
- **Data repositories:** Data repositories for archiving and making data accessible (sometimes linked to the workspaces mentioned above). Agreements on data governance are important here (how long data is retained, who is responsible for access management, etc.). Examples include Dataverse.NL and Yoda.
- **Long-term data repositories:** Data repositories for archiving, access and long-term preservation of data. Examples include 4TU.ResearchData and the DANS Data Stations.

The following infrastructural components play a role in the exchange and reuse of datasets^d (although these are currently still rarely used in practice):

- **Data transfer tools**, which enable datasets to be transferred (securely) (between researchers, from the working environment to the data repository and from the data repository to the working environment)
- **Data access mechanisms**, which regulate the conditions for accessing a dataset. An example is the Data Access Broker (DAB), which gives researchers access to data providers via a DOI (direct

^c [SURF Research Cloud](#) is a portal in which virtual research environments can be built using, among other things, pre-configured workspaces and datasets, or by adding these yourself. Organisations can contribute to the functionality by integrating their computing and data services.

^d In addition, there are encryption and pseudonymisation tools.

access in the case of open access; in the case of access subject to conditions, a link to the data provider's landing page).

- **Access management mechanisms:** access to data and data management environments for individual researchers with whom collaboration takes place (see SRAM – SURF Research Access Management).

It is important to note that the development of research data management infrastructure runs parallel to the Open Science movement regarding the FAIR criteria and the reproducibility crisis, meaning that the distinction between 'research infrastructure' and 'Open Science infrastructure' is often blurred in discussions. SPII's approach is based on the Open Science perspective on RDM infrastructure. In that light, we observe the following:

- A wide variety of RDM infrastructure components, with a landscape that is still very much under development and which, partly as a result, it is difficult for researchers to navigate.
- No or insufficient end-to-end integration: research administration → data management plan → data management environment → (long-term) data repository
- A lack of institution-wide agreements regarding data governance (who is responsible for access, retention periods, etc.)
- Gaps in automation: a data access mechanism that automates the granting of access to datasets under certain conditions (example: Research Data Exchange (RDX), which is insufficiently developed^e).

WHAT WE AIM TO ACHIEVE

1. End-to-end integration where possible through federation
2. Automation where possible to reduce the burden on researchers
3. Common agreements that enable (1) and (2).

Relevant objective NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda

4.4 By 2027, Dutch FAIR research services and infrastructure will be efficiently organised and connected, closely linked to the European digital infrastructure. There will be FAIR data service infrastructures based on major data-sharing initiatives (e.g. SURF, DANS), including a network of FAIR data portals as part of the EOSC.

GAP ANALYSIS

The following gaps have been identified:

- **Gap in research administration:**

^e RDX entails the following: (1) the researcher makes the dataset available under certain conditions by means of a series of questions; (2) the potential user digitally signs a contract for access, thereby committing to comply with the conditions.

- Section 3.3.1 has already addressed the research administration process. With regard to datasets, the aim is to ‘incorporate’ the metadata generated during the rest of the research project that is relevant to the sharing and reuse of research data and to the reproducibility of the research. This is seen as a major opportunity: a link with research administration that makes it possible to incorporate, reuse and further supplement the metadata developed during that process.
- **Gap regarding DMPs:**
 - DMPs are currently mainly static documents and have the character of ‘think before you start’ and sometimes also the character of a contract. However, it is desirable to also use them as a source of information for the rest of the research project. In this context, the possible functions of machine-readable DMPs are discussed here^f.
- **Gap in the transition from processing to archiving/publishing a dataset:**
 - It is desirable that the metadata of research datasets currently in progress be automatically included when researchers archive and/or publish the datasets via a (long-term) data repository. This ensures that the information is recorded in a timely manner and prevents redundant data entry.
- **Gap in (the automation of) data access mechanisms:**
 - Examples of automated data access mechanisms include the Data Access Broker, which connects researchers with providers [via a DOI: direct access for open access, the data provider’s landing page for access subject to conditions], and Research Data Exchange (RDX), which manages both sides of the process (but is not yet sufficiently developed). In this process, the researcher makes the dataset available subject to conditions by means of a series of questions, and the potential user signs a contract setting out the terms of use in order to gain access. In this way, data providers are supported in maintaining control over who uses sensitive data and how, and it becomes attractive for researchers to share sensitive data in a FAIR manner.
- **Gap in national agreements on, among other things, data governance:**
 - This involves national agreements on matters such as data governance, including the allocation of responsibilities for access (particularly when data is transferred to a data repository), as well as the harmonisation of institutional policies (for example, regarding the classification of research data sensitivity).

OVERVIEW OF STAKEHOLDERS

The stakeholders involved include data stewards, administrators and developers of data management environments and data repositories, DCCs and TDCCs, SURF, 4TU.ResearchData and DANS.

^f In terms of tools for creating DMPs, a certain consolidation appears to be taking place around a few tools. Argos, Data Steward Wizard and DMP Online were mentioned in this context. DCC-PO has developed a generic DMP plan for the 36 universities of applied sciences. These are potential starting points for developing machine-readable DMPs with a view to ‘incorporating’ metadata into the rest of the research process.

RECOMMENDATION

- Develop a coherent approach to Research Data Management across the entire data life cycle, from project planning to reuse, in collaboration with the stakeholders. With regard to the Open Science aspects, this involves (1) by carrying forward and further supplementing through the research process the metadata that are relevant to the sharing and reuse of the data and to the reproducibility of the research during the research process, and (2) addressing the aforementioned gaps in the automation of data access mechanisms. SPII Part 2 could address the Open Science aspects, in close coordination with SURF, which plays a coordinating role in connecting and/or developing the research infrastructure of RDM components.

3.3.4 INFRASTRUCTURE SHARING AND SOFTWARE REUSE

CURRENT SITUATION

The Research Software Directory (RSD) has been developed by the eScience Center over the past few years. The aim is to encourage the reuse of research software, link it to other research outputs, and ensure that software use is cited with a view to recognising and valuing the relevant researchers and research software engineers. In addition to the implementation of the RAiD identifier and the SPDX identifier, as well as the metadata standards CFF and Codemeta, the deployment of the RSD means that, from a technical perspective, everything is in place for the archiving of software (in Zenodo or Software Heritage) with a view to linking it to publications.

WHAT WE AIM TO ACHIEVE

Adoption of the aforementioned infrastructural components through the development of Best Practices for Research Software.

Relevant objective NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda

4.7 By 2030, the Dutch open science community will have access to a robust, cost-effective, and sustainable research software ecosystem, which enables the publication and archiving of software in online software repositories (e.g. GitHub, GitLab) by Research Public Organisations (RPOs), as well as integration and interoperability with existing national, international, and domain-oriented archives and Current Research Information Systems.

GAP ANALYSIS

The gap is that the technical components are operational, but their adoption is lacking.

OVERVIEW OF STAKEHOLDERS

Research software engineers, researchers, eScience, TDCCs, DCCs.

RECOMMENDATION

It is recommended that Best Practices be developed for the FAIR archiving and publishing of research software. Shortly after the conclusion of SPII Part 1, the results of a TDCC NES project entitled '[Best Practices for Sustainable Software](#)' will be published. It is possible that this recommendation has already been addressed by this project, or that adapted Best Practices need to be developed for other disciplines.

3.3.5 OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION, DISCOVERY AND ACTIVE DISSEMINATION

CURRENT SITUATION

A significant proportion of research information on Dutch research is not openly available. The portion that is open is available in a fragmented manner. The [Barcelona Declaration](#) – signed by multiple stakeholders in the Netherlands – calls, among other things, for research information to be made open and for sustainable infrastructure to be developed for this purpose.

Since 2023, the discovery and dissemination of Dutch research results has been achieved through the aggregation of metadata from institutional repositories in the [Netherlands Research Portal](#) as part of OpenAIRE.

WHAT WE AIM TO ACHIEVE

MAIN OBJECTIVES

- An infrastructure for making open research information about Dutch research available, with the most comprehensive data collection possible that can be used and analysed by all parties.
- Improvement of the discovery and dissemination of Dutch research results, resulting in increased (inter)national visibility.

Relevant objective NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda

3.2 By 2027, the digital infrastructure for scientific publications and metadata will be sustainable and preferably open, and will support publication, (re-)use and analysis by anyone. This includes the development of a national publication platform and an Open Knowledge Base, as well as support for existing open archives, repositories and infrastructures (such as Publinova) for publications, data, software and other scholarly outputs.

CONCRETE PROPOSALS

- **Counters and metrics:** Counters must be installed on the various components of OSI to track downloads and views of publications, and to measure the reuse of datasets (for example, via [Make Data Count](#)) and research software. Alignment with the Open Science Monitor currently being put out to tender in the Netherlands and the relevant international initiatives ([Open Science Monitoring Initiative](#)) should be sought in this regard.
- **Metadata hub:** The metadata hub brings together information about the research and the metrics by collecting them from the various components of the system, linking them where possible, and making them available as Open Research Information.

- **Discovery layer:** The discovery layer contains the same information as the metadata hub, but presents it in a different way that is suitable for discovery.
- **Active dissemination:** The information in the discovery layer is disseminated via active dissemination to various national and international search engines, aggregation platforms, etc. This should lead to increased visibility of Dutch research.

GAP ANALYSIS

A shared infrastructure containing open research information on Dutch research is currently lacking, resulting in fragmentation (different actors collect and process research information in different ways). Such an infrastructure – referred to here as a metadata hub – should collect the following data:

(1) Research input:

- This concerns data on, amongst other things, individuals, project grants, data management plans and equipment. This information must be collected from institutional systems such as research administration platforms and CRIS systems, and from systems operated by organisations such as NWO and CrossRef, using identifiers such as Grant ID and RAID.
- A significant gap has been identified here, as this information proves difficult to collect in practice because many institutions do not have this information properly organised.

(2) Research output:

- This includes data on publications, datasets, software, patents and events (media appearances).
- This information can often be collected, but it is spread across many sources.

(3) Research outcome:

- This includes data such as views, downloads, forks, scientific citations in peer-reviewed articles, and mentions in social media, news articles and policy documents.
- This information is spread across many sources and is partly held by commercial providers.

Enrichment: It is envisaged that the metadata hub will have mechanisms for quality control of the data to be included and will enrich the collected data using tools (for example, modules that use text and data mining to extract information from the full text of an article regarding, for instance, the research funder, SDGs and the like).

The Netherlands Research Portal (still) has shortcomings regarding the quality and coverage of the repositories (see section 3.3.1) and regarding the functionality of the portal (see the [roadmap](#)).

RECOMMENDATION

- Set up a metadata hub that brings together information about the research and the metrics by collecting them from the various components of the system, linking them where possible, and making them available as Open Research Information.
- Use this information to actively disseminate information about Dutch research via a discovery layer.

3.3.6 FEDERATED AGREEMENT FRAMEWORK, ADDITIONAL FUNCTIONALITY, DESIGN CRITERIA AND PRECONDITIONS

FEDERATED AGREEMENT FRAMEWORK

A federated agreement framework is essential to enable, maintain and further develop the federated structure of OSI. As mentioned earlier, this concerns agreements in the following areas:

- Technical and semantic:
 - PIDs: this concerns the consistent application of persistent identifiers by all parties participating in the federation. The federated diagrams list a number of PIDs that are more or less standard (DOI, ORCID, NBN, SWID), but are often still used inconsistently. In addition, a series of PIDs are considered necessary, the implementation of which is still in its early stages: RAiD (for projects), GrantIDs (for project grants), ROR (for organisations), SPDX identifier (for software licences). This argues for an expansion of the scope and accelerated implementation of the SURF project 'NL-PID implementation'.
 - Metadata: agreements on the use of metadata standards also form part of the framework of agreements. These include the metadata standards Marc21, CFF, Codemeta and the use of common vocabularies/ontologies for metadata descriptions. It should be noted that it is not strictly necessary for a federated connection that the two systems use the same metadata standard. It is possible to build a translation (crosswalk) into the connection (usually an API) to another format/standard, so that both systems can communicate effectively with one another. As the systems are further developed, it is often decided to adopt the 'other format/standard' going forward.
 - In addition, agreements are needed on harmonising the inclusion policy for CRIS/repository systems, definitions of items, common templates for contextual documentation and the data models to be applied.
- Legal:
 - Part of the federated agreement framework relates more to legal matters. These include agreements on data ownership, on harmonising the criteria for sensitive datasets (currently often divided into four categories), agreements on encryption and decryption procedures, data transfer/sharing agreements, and on responsibilities regarding access and data governance.
- Organisational:
 - Organisational issues concerning the federation (including governance, operational organisation, support, training) will be addressed in SPII Part 3.

ADDITIONAL FUNCTIONALITIES, DESIGN CRITERIA AND PRECONDITIONS

In addition to the OSI components and functions proposed above, there are several additional functionalities, design criteria and preconditions that are essential for successful implementation:

- **User-friendliness and workflow support:** Researchers and research support professionals must be optimally supported within a workflow. This means that interfaces are intuitive, processes are streamlined as much as possible, and actions are automated wherever possible.
- **Data storage:** The infrastructure that provides secure and flexible storage options for data, including both open datasets and closed or restricted-access datasets.
- **Quality control:** Administrative checks are carried out by the service organisations on publications in the institutional repositories (including metadata, licences, etc.). An additional option for institutions is to also carry out an academic check to ensure the quality of the uploaded content.
- **Metrics and review options:** The aforementioned metrics and the Post-pub review option (reader comments) mentioned in relation to the national publication aggregator are also important in the context of recognising and valuing non-traditional research publications, such as protocols, reports, etc., which thereby gain in status.

Finally, OSI must comply with the preconditions set out in section 2.3.3.

3.4 TOWARDS AN INTEGRATED REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE FOR OSI

This project has formulated starting points for the development of an integrated reference architecture for OSI. These starting points need to be discussed and further elaborated in a broader context; hence, they are presented here in Appendix C rather than in the main text. It is, however, important to emphasise that such a reference architecture for OSI, which is to be further developed, will have a significant convergent effect. Appendix C illustrates the convergent effect of the reference architecture for digital heritage (DERA) within a landscape of heritage institutions that, in terms of diversity and decentralised structure, bears similarities to the landscape in which OSI will be embedded. The proposal is to view the OSI reference architecture as a first step towards a broader reference architecture for research (HOSA for research).

4. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR SPII PART 2

4.1 DISCUSSION AND EVALUATION OF SPII PART 1

PROCESS

PROJECT GROUP AS A THINK TANK

The Strategic Plan for Integrated Open Science Infrastructure Part 1 before you, subtitled ‘Outlines of an Open Science Infrastructure’, was developed by the SPII Part 1 Project Group. This project group consisted of a small group of experts who worked on this with great enthusiasm and were made available for this purpose by their institutions. The project group acted as a think tank and, in a short period of time (24 March to 16 July 2025) and with limited resources, developed a proposal for an Open Science Infrastructure using a method (use cases → federated diagrams → proposals for federated infrastructure components). This method is described in section 3.2 and Appendix A.

LIMITED CONSULTATION ON VERSION 0.7

In early June, the initial results were set out in version 0.7, which was subsequently discussed in a consultation round with a limited number of stakeholders (due to time constraints). The feedback received has either been incorporated into the present version or is reflected in the discussion below, along with suggestions for addressing this in SPII Part 2.

SPII PART 1 AS A FIRST STEP

Given the project group’s limited time and resources, we are aware that SPII Part 1 requires further detail, elaboration and expansion, and is expected to be amended following a more extensive consultation on a number of aspects. This report should therefore be regarded as a first step towards a fully-fledged strategic plan. Despite the aforementioned limitations, we hope that this plan contains sufficient starting points for a follow-up. See our proposals for SPII Part 2 in section 4.3.

FEEDBACK FROM THE CONSULTATION ROUND

RELATIONSHIP WITH OSNL PROJECTS

During the consultation round, many questions were raised about the relationship between this plan and the projects submitted to OSNL for the Open Science Infrastructure call. The answer lies in the independent method followed by the project group. The fact that some proposals for the Open Science Infrastructure bear a strong resemblance to projects submitted for the OSNL call strengthens, in our view, both the method followed and these project proposals.

LIMITED CONSULTATION

Another point of criticism was the limited consultation, with many indicating that they would have liked to have been more closely involved in the development of SPII.

We view this as a very positive sign: there is clearly a great deal of interest in such a strategic plan, and the active participation of many stakeholders in its further development as part of a follow-up approach therefore seems assured.

USE CASES DO NOT SUFFICIENTLY REFLECT THE ENTIRE RESEARCH CYCLE

Another point of concern raised concerns the use cases on which the federated diagrams are based. It was argued that other use cases have not been developed, such as those relevant to researchers during the conduct of their research. As a result, according to these speakers, the report currently places too much emphasis on sharing research results at the end of the project and pays too little attention to Open Science aspects during the conduct of the research.

Figure 8 (in Appendix A) shows the use cases linked to the research cycle. This demonstrates that no use cases have indeed been developed for the implementation phase of a research project. It is expected that such use cases will be highly discipline-specific. In SPII Part 2, it should be examined whether stakeholders propose use cases for the implementation phase and to what extent this results in additional desired components for the federated infrastructure. We view this as a validation of the methodology followed. Linking the use cases to the research cycle does indeed show that few use cases have been developed for the implementation phase of research. We therefore endorse this limitation of the use cases and advocate that, in the follow-up approach, additional use cases – proposed by stakeholders – be included and that the same methodology (use cases → federated schema → infrastructure proposal) be applied to them.

INFRASTRUCTURE PROPOSALS AND CONCERNS ABOUT SELF-BUILD

Other participants in the consultation round felt that the pros and cons of the more concrete proposals for infrastructure in this report had not been sufficiently elaborated and discussed with the relevant stakeholders. The proposed publication aggregator at national level serves as an example here. There is a fear – partly based on previous experience – that this could lead to the construction of an infrastructure that will be little or not at all used in practice.

We consider it unnecessary to build the publication aggregator ourselves, particularly in light of recent developments regarding the open-sourcing of the Open Research Europe platform.

DECOUPLING FROM EXISTING SYSTEMS

Some participants advocate a more functional approach to OSI components, described in terms of data platforms, data products, data management and tooling (including the use of AI). In other words: avoiding the use of names of existing systems, which are, after all, subject to change. Such an approach would make it clearer that certain modules can be used for multiple functions within OSI. We endorse this and see the development of an OSI reference architecture as a way to achieve this.

4.2 CONCLUSION

The responses to version 0.7 of this plan show that there is considerable interest among stakeholders in a vision and strategy for developing an integrated, coherent infrastructure for Open Science. We

hope that this report is seen as a first step towards this and as a catalyst for further development. In this regard, we wish to emphasise that, in our view, the strength of the report lies in the methodology employed, and we advocate that this methodology – possibly expanded to include more use cases – should also be applied to SPII Part 2. For SPII Part 2, we recommend an approach in the following section.

4.3 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR SPII PART 2

SPLIT INTO PARTS 2 AND 3

The proposal is to split SPII Part 2 into two parts, 2 and 3:

- 2 with a technical focus, aiming to produce concrete proposals for OSI
- 3 with an organisational approach centred on the concrete OSI proposals.

At the start of SPII Part 2, we propose incorporating the suggestions in Annex D into the precise structure and scope of SPII Part 2.

PROPOSAL FOR THE SPII PART 2 WORK PROGRAMME

Figure 7 Overview of the proposed work programme for SPII Part 2

Work package A focused on the technical elaboration of the OSI interfaces:

- A. Development of a reference architecture
- B. Development of metadata schema
- C. Possible expansion and acceleration of the PID implementation project (carried out by SURF Innovation Zone Strengthening Open Science)
- D. Development of APIs and links to discipline-specific research infrastructures
- E. Link with EOSC node

All of the above to be developed in close conjunction with work packages B to E listed below.

Work package B Technical elaboration focused on the proposed OSI federated solutions in collaboration with the relevant stakeholder communities, comprising the following sub-work packages

A. Research administration: Elaboration of the recommendation:

Developing common agreements on the harmonisation of Open Science data and mapping out the technical possibilities for using these systems to feed the rest of the research process with regard to Open Science aspects, drawing on the *lessons learnt* from the various research administration systems currently in use or under development at the different institutions.

B. CRIS/repositories: optimisation and efficiency drive and use as a publication channel:

Implementation of the recommendations:

- CRIS/repository systems:
 - Synchronisation and harmonisation of working methods and inclusion policies
 - Federation of these systems with a view to efficiency and optimisation.
- Redesign of the infrastructure for publishing:
 - Further development of the potential of a national repository/publication aggregator/publication platform, particularly for non-traditional publications and innovative publication formats such as the PRC model.
 - Connector between publication aggregator and KB eDepot
 - Publication aggregator as a starting point for making content available to the general public

C. Infrastructure for sharing and reusing (sensitive) data: implementation of the recommendations:

- Develop a coherent approach to Research Data Management across the entire data life cycle, from project planning to reuse, in collaboration with stakeholders. With regard to the Open Science aspects, this involves (1) carrying forward through the research process the metadata that are relevant to the sharing and reuse of the data and to the reproducibility of the research during the research process, and (2) addressing the aforementioned gaps in the automation of data access mechanisms.
- SPII's approach to Open Science aspects, Part 2, in close coordination with SURF, which plays a coordinating role in connecting and/or developing the research infrastructure of RDM components.

D. Sharing infrastructure and reusing research software: elaboration of the recommendation:

- Develop Best Practices for the FAIR archiving and publishing of research software, in addition to the results of the TDCC NES project '[Best Practices for Sustainable Software](#)'.

E. Metadata hub for ORI and Discovery layer and active dissemination: implementation of the recommendations:

- Set up a metadata hub that brings together information about the research and the metrics by collecting them from the various components of the system, linking them where possible, and making them available as Open Research Information.
- Use this information to actively disseminate information about Dutch research via a discovery layer.

Work package C: Prioritisation, roadmap development, development of business cases and cost-benefit analyses for proposed ‘data products’

We envisage a third work package which – based on the results of work packages A and B – establishes priorities for the roadmap to be drawn up, develops 2 or 3 data products, as detailed in work package B, elaborates on these in terms of cost-benefit analysis and business case, and on that basis delivers deliverable 3 (see below).

Deliverables:

(1) Technical infrastructure elements:

- Reference architecture/target architecture
- Metadata schema
- Technical standards and agreements on interfaces, including the EOSC-NL node interface

(2) Proposal for a federated set of agreements

- Proposal for a technical and semantic agreement framework arising from the above-mentioned work packages
- Proposal for legal agreements arising from the aforementioned work packages.
- Aligned with agreements regarding the EOSC-NL node.

(3) OSI roadmap and proposals for development and implementation 2026–2029

- Proposals for the development, in the period 2026–2029, of several ‘data products’ that are a high priority for OSI, including a business case and cost-benefit analysis.
- Outline of the OSI roadmap for the longer term

Implementation:

- Through a project group to be formed, in which project group members take on the coordination of a work package and invite stakeholders to participate in working groups and/or workshops relating to a work package.
- If possible, the proposal is to make all project communications public, allowing anyone who wishes to do so to participate or provide feedback, following the example of [W3C](#) (this does, however, require an environment in which this is possible).

SPII PART 3

Once the deliverables of SPII Part 2 have been adopted, the organisational aspects surrounding these deliverables can be developed. This should be done in close coordination with the organisational developments surrounding the EOSC-NL node. The following should be considered:

- Governance structure
- Operational organisation
- Funding.

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A1. INTRODUCTION

The project group developed the OSI largely on the basis of use cases involving workflows of researchers and research support professionals. This was done with a view to developing the OSI as much as possible from the bottom up. Most use cases focused on the FAIR sharing of research results, which the project group regards as the main function of the OSI.

In summary, the method comprises the following steps:

- For each use case, based on the steps in the workflow, the necessary technical elements were identified, along with which of these should be federated; the social and human elements that play a role in the workflow steps; and the federated agreements required regarding standards and interoperability.
- In a second step, for each domain, the federated solutions identified in the use cases were presented in a federated schema containing the list of federated agreements (technical, semantic, legal) and the modules to be connected by the federated solution.
- The federated solutions as presented in the federated diagrams formed the basis for the proposals in Chapter 3 for the various components of the OSI infrastructure.

Figure 8 Use cases linked to the research cycle [LMA Research Data Management Working Group]

Figure 7 shows the use cases linked to the research cycle (the use cases in yellow are shown twice because they may be relevant to multiple phases). The use cases are plotted against the research phases to which they primarily belong. Figure 7 shows that few use cases have been developed for the research implementation phase. It is expected that such use cases will have a strongly

disciplinary character. In SPII Part 2, it should be examined whether stakeholders propose use cases for the ‘ ‘ implementation phase and to what extent this results in additional desired components for the federated infrastructure.

The following sections present the use cases and the federated diagrams.

A2. OSC: USE CASES AND FEDERATED SCHEMA

The following use cases were developed for OSC:

- Publishing non-traditional research results
- Publishing an article in a traditional journal – in the current situation and in the proposed desired situation
- Publishing according to the PRC model
- Access to scientific publications for a wide audience

These use cases are presented on the following pages.

<p>Use case: Publishing a report as an example of a non-traditional research result</p>	<p>Technical components</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federated solution for CRIS/repositories: a mechanism ensuring that a report or other output with multiple authors from different research institutions is exchanged between the repositories/CRIS systems in such a way that a single DOI is assigned, all authors receive ORCIDs, and only one service organisation processes the metadata (deduplication and efficiency)
<p>Workflow steps:</p> <p>Researcher(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare final version • Client approval • Request a DOI from the institutional repository/CRIS service organisation and include it in the report • Select a licence and include it in the report • Create a PDF and deposit it in the repository/CRIS <p>Repository/CRIS organisation (library):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata tagging, including checking for PIDs (ORCID, ROR, DOI, etc.) 	<p>Social/human elements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repository/CRIS service organisation (usually the library) offers services ‘as a publisher’ with the addition of PIDs and metadata in Marc21 format. • Repository/CRIS service organisations at universities, universities of applied sciences (PubliNova) and other knowledge institutions harmonise their policies on inclusion and metadata tagging
<p>Result: publication and dissemination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report registered in CRIS • Report published in repository [§] • Metadata in library catalogue, automatic inclusion in WorldCat; also in Google and other search engines 	<p>Standards and interoperability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PIDs: ORCID, ROR, DOI, possibly RAiD in the future • Metadata standard Marc21 • Same formats for the different types of output
<p>Comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We make no distinction between CRIS and repository: these are sometimes in a single application (Pure), sometimes in two different applications. (CRIS is a registration system; a repository is a document storage system.) Both fulfil a function in the area of metadata collection with a link to the storage of objects. • The WUR workflow is shown here. It must be checked whether this is comparable across the board. • The federated solution needs to be technically developed. The combination of OpenAIRE Provide, OpenAIRE Graph and OpenAIRE Broker may be suitable for this purpose. <p>Conclusion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In this use case, the institutional repository acts as the publication channel to the world. 	

[§] Institutional repositories mainly contain textual research output. The term ‘repository’ is also used for data repositories, which contain research datasets.

PUBLISHING AN ARTICLE IN A TRADITIONAL JOURNAL – CURRENT SITUATION

<p>Use case: Publishing a journal article [current situation]</p> <p>Researcher(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drafting a manuscript • As a journal: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Choosing a journal and ensuring compliance with any funding conditions and institutional policies ○ <i>Submit, review, rebuttal, acceptance</i> • As a PRC model: manuscript on a preprint server, possibly later in an (overlay) journal <p>CRIS/Repository organisation (usually the library):</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 33%;">As a subscription journal</td> <td style="width: 33%;">As a journal with a Read & Publish deal or a Publish deal</td> <td style="width: 33%;">As an OA journal without a Publish deal</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Metadata will be received later via Scopus or similar</td> <td>Library receives notification of acceptance via the publisher</td> <td>Metadata will be received later via Scopus or similar</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Requests AAM from author for inclusion in repository</td> <td>Receives metadata and published article for inclusion in the repository</td> <td>Harvests the published article for inclusion in the repository</td> </tr> </table> <p>Result</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Published article in journal • Subsequent inclusion of the metadata in the repository and CRIS (often via a submission from the publisher or Scopus, etc.) • Inclusion of full text either via (manual) downloads or via a request to the author for AAM 			As a subscription journal	As a journal with a Read & Publish deal or a Publish deal	As an OA journal without a Publish deal	Metadata will be received later via Scopus or similar	Library receives notification of acceptance via the publisher	Metadata will be received later via Scopus or similar	Requests AAM from author for inclusion in repository	Receives metadata and published article for inclusion in the repository	Harvests the published article for inclusion in the repository	<p>Technical components</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Journal browser – assistance in choosing a journal • Metadata via publisher, via Scopus etc. <p>Social/human factors</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The CRIS/repository service organisation is not, or hardly, <i>in the loop</i> between the author and the publisher/preprint service and is therefore lagging behind • Researchers often have little motivation to request the full text of an article published long ago (perceived as bureaucratic and no longer useful) <p>Standards and interoperability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PIDs: ORCID, ROR, DOI, possibly RAiD in the future • Metadata standard Marc21
As a subscription journal	As a journal with a Read & Publish deal or a Publish deal	As an OA journal without a Publish deal										
Metadata will be received later via Scopus or similar	Library receives notification of acceptance via the publisher	Metadata will be received later via Scopus or similar										
Requests AAM from author for inclusion in repository	Receives metadata and published article for inclusion in the repository	Harvests the published article for inclusion in the repository										
<p>Conclusion: CRIS/repository handles registration and storage after the actual publication.</p>												

PUBLISHING AN ARTICLE IN A TRADITIONAL JOURNAL – DESIRED SITUATION

Use case: Publishing a journal article [desired situation]			Technical components		
<p>Researcher(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparing a manuscript • Deposit in CRIS/repository • As a journal: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Select a journal and ensure compliance with any funding conditions and institutional policy ○ <i>Submit, review, rebuttal, acceptance</i> • As a PRC model: choose a preprint server (see below) <p>CRIS/Repository organisation (usually the library):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata tagging and PID check (technical and administrative checks) • Based on the authors' choice, via the federated 'publication channel' solution to the desired publisher (or preprint server, see below) • If not connected to the 'publication channel', then the metadata-tagged article is submitted via the author's submission procedure to the publisher 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Journal browser – assistance in choosing a journal • Federated solution for CRIS/repositories: a mechanism ensuring that a report or other output with multiple authors from different research institutions is exchanged between the repositories/CRIS systems in such a way that a single DOI is assigned, all authors receive ORCIDs, and only one service organisation adds metadata (deduplication and efficiency) (see OpenAIRE mechanisms for this) • Federated 'publication channel' solution: the manuscript, supplemented by the library, is submitted to the desired publication channel based on the author's choice. This could initially be developed for preprint servers and for publishers with Publish deals • Federated solution for 'feed-back of published version': see Jisc's publication router 		
Subscription journal	Journal with a Read & Publish deal or a Publish deal	OA journal without a Publish deal	<p>Social/human elements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The CRIS/repository service organisation is in place and adds value for both the author and the publisher/preprint service: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Metadata ○ PID check ○ Trust: the manuscript originates from a reputable research institution, is by an existing author(s) at that institution and is traceable (administrative check) • Added value from the perspective of researchers and publishers requires further investigation. • Requires a shift in researchers' mindset to first submit their draft article to the repository for the addition of metadata and PIDs and to specify the desired publication route. 		
If accepted, AAM and metadata already in CRIS/repository	Library receives notification of <i>acceptance</i> via publisher Metadata already in CRIS/repository; AAM to be replaced later by published version	Metadata already in CRIS/repository Harvest published article for inclusion in repository			
Return of published version to CRIS/repository	Return of published version to CRIS/repository	Return of published version to CRIS/repository			

<p>Result:</p> <p>Published article in journal</p> <p>Metadata/AAM in early stage in repository.</p>	<p>Standards and interoperability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PIDs: ORCID, ROR, DOI, possibly RAiD in the future • Metadata standard: Marc21
<p>Conclusion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In this setup, the CRIS/repository becomes the first step in the publication of journal articles. • Further investigation is needed to determine whether this provides sufficient added value to both researchers and publishers • This may require scaling up the service organisation around CRIS systems and repositories at the institutions (more metadata tagging work) • Publication channel could initially be linked to Diamond journals 	

Use case: Publishing an article according to the PRC model			Technical components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federated solution for CRIS/repositories: a mechanism ensuring that a report or other output with multiple authors from different research institutions is exchanged between the repositories/CRIS systems in such a way that a single DOI is assigned, all authors receive ORCIDs, and only one service organisation handles metadata (deduplication and efficiency) • Federated ‘publication channel’ solution: the manuscript, supplemented by the library, is submitted to the desired publication channel based on the author’s choice. May be developed first for preprint servers and for publishers with Publish deals • Federated solution: Notify mechanism: COAR’s Notify mechanism works for publication via overlay journals; investigate whether this could also work between preprint servers/ORE platforms and repositories • Federated solution ‘return of published version’: for publication in journals or in ORI, see Jisc’s publication router • Platform X-NI: potential platform for Dutch publications with functionality comparable to ORE. • NL Aggregator publication objects: a platform that could be set up for Dutch publications with preprint functionality, potentially combinable with X-NL
Workflow steps: Researcher(s): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher submits manuscript to institutional repository • Library enriches manuscript with metadata <p>A. Using the federated ‘Publication Channel’ solution, the manuscript is forwarded from the repository to the desired publication channel based on the author’s choice. This immediately ensures a certain level of integrity of the manuscript at the preprint server (as it is, after all, from an author at an established research institution).</p> <p>B. If ‘Publication Channel’ has not been implemented, the author must submit the manuscript to the preprint server themselves</p>			
ArXiv; MedRxiv; BioRxiv	Open Research Europe/ F1000 [or platform X-NL]	NL Aggregator publication objects	Social/human elements <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication culture varies between disciplines; depends on the communities within disciplines • Time to publication can be an incentive • Possible target: 10–15% of all publications following the PRC model.
Post-publication peer review Revise manuscript if necessary	Author finds two peer reviewers themselves; possible revisions to manuscript	Post-publication peer review Revise manuscript if necessary	
Submit to SCOAP3 journals or other journals		Submit via Notify to an overlay journal	
Editorial board/Peer review		Editorial board/Peer review	
Publication of peer-reviewed version	Publication of peer-reviewed version	Publication of peer-reviewed version in repository	
Link to repository (via DOI) and mechanism for returning full text	Connection to repository (via DOI transfer) and mechanism for returning full text	Connection via Notify between overlay journal and repository	

<p>Result:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication of preprint and/or peer-reviewed article • In the case of a federated ‘publication channel’ solution: (1) manuscript has been received; (2) certain guarantee of the manuscript’s integrity at the preprint server or publication platform. • Return of full text to repository via federated solution 	<p>Standards and interoperability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PIDs: ORCID, ROR, DOI, possibly RAiD in the future • Metadata standard Marc21
<p>Comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The added value of an NL Aggregator for publication objects lies in the following: (1) from a <i>composability</i> perspective, it is easier to create publication channels from a single platform to preprint servers than from dozens of repositories; (2) the implementation of the Notify mechanism for overlay journals is only of interest to overlay journals if there is sufficient volume; (3) if a post-publication peer review option is also set up, then non-traditional research output can also be reviewed and thus recognised/valued. • Peer review: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Post-publication peer review: here we mean comments by readers on a published version. ○ Peer review: here we refer to the peer review process, coordinated by a journal editor or initiated by the author themselves (author-centred peer review). Regarding the openness of peer review, there are 7 characteristics (see, among others,¹³). 	

<p>Use case: Use of and access to scientific information for the general public</p>	<p>Technical components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Portal • Aggregation of journalistic articles • Aggregation of scientific articles • Wikipedia-style publishing system • AI tools
<p>Workflow steps:</p> <p>Users for whom no translation is required (findability and accessibility are bottlenecks – good overview of public sources (incorporate AI tools such as RAG)):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approx. 50% of scientific articles are already open • Findability: Google Scholar, Dimensions, PubMed • Findability and Accessibility: raising awareness of Open Alex, OpenAire: <p>If no access (Closed Access), then no real solution; count the number of turnaways, identify areas of high interest, and take action accordingly.</p> <p>Users for whom translation is required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Journalistic translation: Groen Kennisnet, NEMO Kennislink, science supplements in newspapers, ... • Direct access to scientific articles with translation: set up an authoritative portal: here the information includes support (e.g. AI summary of the top 10 search results) • Develop a ‘Wikipedia’-style page on a number of frequently requested topics by various universities – active public outreach by scientists: a channel for scientists to engage with the public {who is responsible for quality?} 	<p>Social/human elements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Editorial team • Commitment from universities to science communication for the general public • Counting towards recognition and appreciation
<p>Result:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science portal aimed at the Dutch public 	<p>Standards and interoperability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperable with repositories and the Dutch research portal • AI processing always linked to the original source
<p>Comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The general public is primarily interested in current affairs, to which science does not always have an answer. Possible solution: build a portal around a number of topical themes. • The portal could potentially be limited to providing access to open scientific articles, supported by AI-generated summaries. 	

Functions: Federated CRIS/institutional repositories and institutional repositories as a publication channel	
Federated solution(s)	Agreement framework for the federation
<p>Federated CRIS/institutional repositories: A mechanism that ensures that a report or other output with multiple authors from different research institutions is exchanged between repositories/CRIS systems in such a way that a single DOI is assigned, all authors are assigned ORCIDs, and only one service organisation provides metadata (deduplication and efficiency). [e.g. possible through a combination of OpenAIRE PROVIDE, OpenAIRE Graph and OpenAIRE Broker].</p> <p>Federated solution ‘return of published version’: for publication in journals or in ORE (mechanism similar to Jisc’s Publication Router).</p>	<p>Federated CRIS/institutional repositories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmonisation of CRIS/repository inclusion policies • Agreement framework regarding the metadata tagging of research output by authors from multiple institutions in CRIS/repositories: For example: the institution that is primarily responsible registers the output and sends a notification to other relevant institutions in the Netherlands. The relevant institution obtains the metadata. Archiving of objects based on DOI in a single repository (responsible institution) • Harmonisation of metadata policy and PID policy (see also below) • Introduction of ROR as an institutional identifier at multiple levels (institution/department)
<p>Institutional repositories as a publication channel: NL Aggregator of publication objects with publication channels:</p> <p>(a) Aggregation at national level of publication objects from the CRIS/repository systems. May be supplemented with a post-publication review option.</p> <p>(b) Publication channels: the manuscript, supplemented by the service organisations, is submitted to the desired publication channel based on the author’s choice. May first be developed for preprint servers, for the ORE platform, and for publishers with Publish deals</p> <p>(c) Federated solution Notify mechanism: Making COAR’s Notify mechanism operational for the aggregator at national level</p>	
<p>Modules for connecting the federation</p>	<p>Institutional repositories as a publication channel:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The starting point is federated CRIS systems/institutional repositories with an associated set of agreements (see above) • Harmonisation of the policies of the service organisations (usually the libraries) regarding the repositories and CRIS systems, in terms of inclusion policy, metadata and PIDs, and the timing of providing the input. This may require an expansion of these service organisations due to increased volume and higher demands (particularly regarding timing). • A shift in researchers’ mindset: it requires a shift in researchers’ mindset to first send their draft article to the repository for the addition of metadata and PIDs and to specify the desired publication route.
<p>Federated CRIS/institutional repositories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CRIS/institutional repository systems 	
<p>Institutional repositories as a publication channel:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Library eDepot (archiving/back-up) • DOI registries • ROR registries • Repository aggregator – IRs • Repository aggregator – OpenAire, Open Indexing 	

Explanation:

We propose two steps:

- **Optimisation and efficiency improvements to the CRIS/repository systems:** a federation for entering publication objects and their metadata (efficiency and deduplication) and a version of the Jisc publication router to automate the harvesting of full text as much as possible.
- **Utilising the CRIS/repository infrastructure as a publication channel:** In the process of output registration → institutional repository → aggregation, the focus is on registration (retrospectively) and ensuring open access. With these infrastructure components, the institutions already handle part of the publication process that makes academic output discoverable. Particularly for output that does not go to publishers, this process is effectively already the step from internal document to public availability, as outlined above for research reports. In this process, some document types also already receive 'institutional' branding. This 'publishing function' could be utilised much more effectively than is currently the case

Other points:

- In the long term, the aim may be to replace CRIS systems with federated solutions (see the SOLID project by SURF with Ghent University)
- Efficiency gains, the elimination of duplicate records and higher full-text coverage in repositories will ensure higher-quality Green OA for Dutch publications.
- A clearer distinction between the repository (open access to objects) and CRIS (output registration at local level by authors and support teams) is needed to, on the one hand, make the process less redundant and, on the other hand, to harmonise it further for the benefit of aggregators and end-users.
- Facilitating the publication of non-traditional research results (including an option for post-publication review); preprints, and publication via the PRC model (overlay journals and possibly via ORE)
- Contributing to higher quality dissemination (and thus visibility).

A3. RDSM: USE CASES AND FEDERATED DIAGRAMS

The following use cases were drawn up for RDSM:

- Sharing of sensitive data
- Reuse of sensitive data
- Publishing single-use research software related to a publication
- Publishing reusable research software

These are presented on the pages below.

SHARING SENSITIVE DATA

Use case: sharing sensitive datasets	Technical components
Steps in the workflow: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers must be able to deposit sensitive data in a secure environment, including information on ownership and the method of obtaining access (data availability statement). • The degree of sensitivity of the data determines the level of protection and access control (this implies that criteria for determining this – low/medium/high/extreme – are available) • Researchers must be able to publish metadata relating to the dataset 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data transfer tools that ensure the security of the transfer (secure data transfer tools) • Rule-based access mechanisms [data brokers [DAB, RDX] • Encryption of data at the storage location • Decryption • Encryption key management • Backup methods/schedules, system maintenance, encryption/decryption test procedures • Multi-factor authentication/access control Social/human elements <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ownership (and responsibilities) must be clearly defined. In particular, when the researcher is no longer employed by the institution. Who is the point of contact? • Data transfer/sharing agreement (data access committee) • Policies/procedures for access, including ethical and legal preconditions • Risk management
Results <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deposit dataset (+ access guidelines, contextual information, processing tools, consent information, etc.) • Citation details for dataset • Publish metadata 	Standards and interoperability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licence types • Metadata • File formats
Explanation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In practice, the sharing and reuse of open datasets already works relatively well. The main bottleneck in this regard is the often inadequate metadata of the datasets, which can limit their discoverability and usability. 	

REUSE OF SENSITIVE DATA FROM PREVIOUS RESEARCH

Use case: reuse of sensitive data from previous research	Technical components <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Secure environment for data analysis (<i>compute-to-data</i> for highly sensitive data [SANE] or data download permitted) Rule-based access mechanisms [data brokers [DAB, RDX] Data transfer tools
Conditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data is stored in a secure environment Including associated licence and responsibilities (who grants access, who is granted access) and under what conditions Sufficient descriptive metadata Researcher: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Upon request, the data-managing institution must grant permission [bottleneck: often the researcher in question is no longer employed] Access is granted; encryption keys are transferred Reuse and publication of the results of the reuse Citation of dataset 	Social/human elements <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear agreements on with whom the data may be shared (knowledge security assessment framework) Quality of metadata and documentation of the context Data curation
Result <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reuse of dataset Citation of dataset 	Standards and interoperability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> PIDs to locate and cite the dataset File formats Date documentation Licences and contracts Context (how was the data generated, what technical equipment was used; can another researcher understand the data)
<p>There are four options for finding datasets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Search engines (such as DataCite Search (by DataCite), Dataset Search (by Google) and Mendeley Data (Elsevier) Publication aggregators with a dataset filter (such as Dimensions.ai, Lens.org, OpenAire) Harvesters (such as ODISSEI) Data repositories (such as DANS, 4TU.ResearchData) 	

PUBLISHING SINGLE-USE RESEARCH SOFTWARE RELATED TO A PUBLICATION

<p>Publishing single-use research software related to a publication</p>	<p>Technical components</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Archiving solution (e.g. 4TU.ResearchData, Zenodo or Software Heritage); version control system
<p>Workflow steps</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe script/code by means of documentation • Deposit script/code and documentation, ensuring that the following are included: metadata with a link to the dataset, a link to the publication (and, where applicable, a link to the project identifier) and licence. • Optional: register with the Research Software Directory (this happens automatically when you deposit your work in 4TU.ResearchData; RSD also harvests metadata from Zenodo). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Registry for discoverability: Research Software Directory • PID resolvers • Social/human elements • Quality of the documentation • Curation of the documentation (version control) • Recognition upon release (based on <i>contribution guidelines</i> if there are multiple software engineers) • SBOM – Software Bill of Materials (still under development; list of aspects of open-source software including dependencies, security risks and vulnerabilities).
<p>Result</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findable and reusable research software package (for reproducibility) 	<p>Standards and interoperability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PIDs (DOI and/or SHHID for software; DOI for publications and datasets; ORCID for researchers and software engineers; RAiD for projects) • Metadata standards • API standards • Licences
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The RAiD identifier and the SPDX identifier, along with the metadata standards CFF and Codemeta (exchange scheme for software metadata), already exist but need to be more widely adopted. Technically speaking, everything is in place for the archiving of software with a view to linking it to publications. In SPII Part 2, this could be developed into a generally accepted ‘Research Software Management Framework’ in order to encourage its adoption. • The Research Software Directory acts as a link between software publications, data, projects, people and organisations. 	

PUBLISHING REUSABLE RESEARCH SOFTWARE

<p>Publishing reusable research software</p>	<p>Technical components</p> <p><i>In the software developer’s computing environment:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Version control system • Testing/CI infrastructure (such as linters, unit and integration test frameworks, and the hardware to run them). <p><i>(Inter)national level:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Archiving solution (e.g. 4TU.ResearchData or Zenodo) • Registry for discoverability: Research Software Directory • PID resolvers
<p>Workflow steps</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Version control platform for the source code (GitHub/GitLab). • Choosing a licence (see e.g. TLDRLegal) • Applying a versioning scheme such as semantic versioning. • Make the software citable by adding the relevant metadata using, for example, CFF • Ensuring software quality (e.g. coding style, static analysis, tests, CI infrastructure) • Creating releases and archiving them with a unique identifier (e.g. a DOI from Zenodo). In addition, a DOI for the collection of all versions (concept DOI on Zenodo). • Making documentation available • Publishing the software on the relevant registries, such as the Research Software Directory, bio.tools, ASCL.net, etc. • Where applicable, also publishing <i>contribution guidelines</i>, <i>issue tracking</i> and governance, SBOM, etc. • Register with the Research Software Directory (when depositing in 4TU.ResearchData, this happens automatically; RSD also harvests metadata from Zenodo; often the metadata still needs to be supplemented). 	<p>Social/human elements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of the documentation, tests, etc. • Curation of the documentation (version control) • Recognition upon publication (based on <i>contribution guidelines</i> if multiple software engineers are involved, use of citation metadata) • SBOM – Software Bill of Materials (still under development; list of aspects of open-source software including <i>dependencies</i>, security risks and vulnerabilities. • Linking the research software to related research outputs and activities (publications, data, projects) as well as people and organisations. This is what the Research Software Directory offers.
<p>Result</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findable, reusable and citable research software package • Improved reproducibility 	<p>Standards and interoperability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PIDs (for software: DOI, SWID; also DOI for publications and datasets; ORCID for researchers and software engineers; RAiD for projects) • Metadata standards such as CFF for citation metadata and Codemeta for software descriptions. • API standards • Licences (using SPDX identifiers – <i>standardised abbreviations for common open source software licences</i>)
<p>Explanation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The RAiD identifier, the SPDX identifier and the metadata standards CFF and Codemeta (exchange scheme for software metadata) already exist, but need to be more widely adopted. Technically speaking, everything is in place for the archiving of software with a view to linking it to publications. In SPII Part 2, this could be developed into a generally accepted ‘Research Software Management Framework’ in order to encourage its adoption. • The Research Software Directory acts as a link between software publications, data, projects, people and organisations. 	

Function: sharing and reuse of (sensitive) data	
<p>Federated solution(s)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data management environments (such as Yoda) • Data storage (storage during research; often fully integrated with a data management environment, and may or may not be shared) • Data repositories (Yoda, for example, offers an archiving option, but without functionality for long-term preservation) • Long-term data repositories (with long-term preservation functionality, such as DANS, 4TU.ResearchData) • Data transfer tools that ensure the security of the transfer (secure data transfer tools) • Rule-based access mechanisms [data brokers [such as DAB, RDX] • Access management mechanisms: access to data and the data management environment for individual researchers with whom collaboration takes place (e.g. SRAM (SURF Research Access Management); multi-factor authentication • Secure environment for data analysis (<i>compute-to-data</i> for highly sensitive data [such as SANE]^h) 	<p>Agreement framework for the federation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmonisation of criteria for sensitive data • Agreements on encryption/decryption procedures • Agreements on responsibilities regarding access and data governance • Agreements on data transfer/sharing • Agreements on risk management
<p>Modules for connecting the federation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data management environments and data repositories • Data management environments and (long-term) data storage environments • Data management environments and data analysis environments • Connections to the research administration environment 	
<p>Explanation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We distinguish between 8 federated components. Some data management environments offer multiple components in one. For example, Yoda offers data management, storage and archiving. • Connections (end-to-end integration) between research administration – including data management plans – on the one hand, and the research process on the other, in a way that facilitates the researcher’s work, are desirable. • Data storage can be organised federatively or on an institutional basis. Data storage can be regarded as part of the research infrastructure. 	

^h <https://www.surf.nl/themas/onderzoekinfrastructuur/sane-veilige-omgeving-voor-analyse-van-gevoelige-data>

FEDERATED RSM SCHEME

Function: sharing and reusing research software	
Federated solution(s) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Software Directory • PID resolvers 	Agreement framework for the federation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PIDs for software (such as DOIs or SWID) • SPDX identifier for licences • Metadata standards CFF and Codemeta (exchange scheme for software metadata) • Use of the software management plan¹⁴
By linking the federation modules <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repositories such as Zenodo, Software Heritage, 4TU.ResearchData • Version control platforms such as GitHub, GitLab, etc. 	
Explanation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The DOI/SWID identifiers, the SPDX identifier and the metadata standards CFF and Codemeta (exchange scheme for software metadata) already exist, but need to be more widely adopted. Technically speaking, everything is in place for the archiving of software with a view to linking it to publications. In SPII Part 2, this could be developed into a generally accepted 'Research Software Management Framework' in order to encourage its adoption. • With regard to collaborating on and using open-source research software, Github or GitLab is used. The following points should be noted: Github is currently mostly used by research software developers with private accounts, which leads to fragmentation and confusion about where things are located. In addition to a general site, GitLab also has local implementations at some institutions, which are not accessible to others. 	

A4. ORI: USE CASES AND FEDERATED SCHEMA

Two use cases were developed for ORI:

- evaluation of a research group
- analysis of the research landscape with a view to gaining new insights

These use cases are presented below, followed by a federated schema.

EVALUATION OF A RESEARCH GROUP

Use case: Evaluate a research group	Technical components <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CRIS and institutional systems (project management system, HR system, financial system) • Funders' database (Cordis, NWO, ...) • Citation database • Altmetrics database
Steps in the workflow <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define research and staff participation in the group • Which projects did they participate in and for how many FTEs? • List per project: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ FTE participants ○ Grant information ○ External collaboration partners ○ Research output (including patents) ○ Equipment • Output: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Publications: #, FAIR score; Research impact: normalised citation score; Societal impact: media ○ Software: #, FAIR score, GitHub stars & forks ○ Data: #, FAIR score, volume; reuse/downloads ○ Patents: #, royalties €; # licence holders ○ Collaboration partners: # academic, # industry/government; countries/global ○ Research equipment: # usage, value 	Social/human elements <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SEP protocol • Research intelligence support • Valorisation office to select and validate research output • Linking research output to projects (currently missing) and data on collaborations (also missing)
Result <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of production • Insight into impact • Insight into value for money 	Standards and interoperability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata standards for outputs, individuals and projects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PIDs: DOI, ORCID, RAiD, GrantID
Explanation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External systems are used to measure the impact of research output (e.g. Open Alex and CrossRef for citations). These figures are usually a proxy for the actual impact, which is difficult to measure objectively. 	

ANALYSIS OF THE RESEARCH LANDSCAPE WITH A VIEW TO GAINING NEW INSIGHTS

<p>Use-case Analysis of the research landscape for new insights [example: benchmark for a specific topic].</p>	<p>Technical components (example) Altmetrics, PubMed, Databricks, Power BI</p>
<p>Steps in the workflow</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Select scope (which institutions, which topics) ▪ Create classifier/apply it to publications ▪ Create dataset selections and pull in additional information sources ▪ Build dashboard 	<p>Social/human elements Research intelligence team</p>
<p>Result</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>Dashboard</u> 	<p>Standards and interoperability DOI, ROR, MESH (or other vocabulary)</p>
<p>Explanation:</p> <p>See two examples: https://app.powerbi.com/view?r=eyJrIjoieYjdMOTJkYTEtZWNmMi00NWU0LTlkYzgtNjhkOTBkMzc5YWE0liwidCI6IjQ2MmE5YzljLTJkYTYtNGJmYi1iMzE4LTBmODMwNDNmZTQ5YiIsImMiOjh9 https://epdos.nl/nl/rarediseasemonitor/</p>	

Open Research Information	
<p>Federated solution(s)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata hub: collects metadata <i>and</i> connects related metadata 	<p>Agreement framework for the federation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information exchange between federated modules using OpenAIRE CERIF <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Currently OpenAIRE CERIF 1.2.0 ○ Extend to Dutch requirements; agreement via EduStandaard.nl • Making connections using PIDS: ROR, ORCID, DOI, RAiD, Grant ID, SWHID, RRID, ISSN, ISBN, ISNI, WikiData, EPIC, ARK
<p>Modules to be connected by the federation:</p> <p>Research input entities: organisational units, persons, grants, projects, data management plans, equipment [Within NL-OSI: to be collected for research administration platform, CRIS systems] [Outside NL-OSI: to be collected from, amongst others, NWO API, CrossRef, FundRef & Grant ID, RAID]</p> <p>Research output entities: publications, datasets, software, patents, events (e.g. media performances) [Within NL-OSI: to be collected from the CRIS systems; data/software/institutional repositories, publication platforms] [Outside NL-OSI: to be collected from, among others, CrossRef, DataCite,...]</p> <p>Research outcome entities: views, downloads, commits, stars, forks, citations (scientific; references in peer-reviewed articles), mentions (societal; references in news articles, policy documents, etc.) [Within NL-OSI: views and downloads to be collected from CRIS systems; data/software/institutional repositories, publication platforms] [Outside NL-OSI: views & downloads to be collected from publishers (article-level COUNTER reports) and OpenAIRE; commits, stars & forks on external Git platforms (e.g. GitHub, Codeberg, GitLab, etc.); citations from Open Citations; mentions from Crossref Event Tracker.]</p> <p>Enrichment of Research entities: Modules that text/data mine full text of articles for funder information, SDGs, other labels, etc. [Within OSI, code algorithms used for inferencing, text mining, etc. are shared in the Software module]</p>	
<p>Explanation: OpenAIRE currently collects and connects federated research input, output and outcome entities and performs enrichments from various sources, both within and outside the NL-OSI (OSI = the proposed Open Science Infrastructure)</p>	

USE CASE: RESEARCH ADMINISTRATION AND COMPLIANCE

<p>Research administration and regulatory compliance</p>	<p>Technical components</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative platform in which various components are available in an integrated manner (such as a data management plan tool, ethical review, GDPR registration) • A storage environment for administrative data relating to research projects for each institution • Preferably a link to other administrative environments within the institution (finance, HR, project control, CRIS)
<p>Workflow steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers must be enabled to carry out all administrative tasks relating to data management for their research project with minimal time investment and as little duplication of effort as possible • This includes, amongst other things, data management (before, during and after the research), software management plan, Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), ethics review, and contracts with companies before, during and after the research. In addition, it is integrated with links to advisers within the institutions on these topics. A workflow aspect has been incorporated to guide the researcher through this process. • Administrative data relating to the research project are verifiable and stored • Including data licences and responsibilities (who grants access, who is granted access) and under what conditions, and who is responsible for deleting or retaining data for longer periods (data governance). 	<p>Social/human elements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A support desk and/or data support organisation • Clear agreements on which administrative actions are required
<p>Result</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-quality administrative data relating to the research project • Research data documentation is available and usable • Direct link to support 	<p>Standards and interoperability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PIDs to identify research projects (RAiD, Grant-ID) • Data documentation • Licences and contracts
<p>Explanation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This does not apply exclusively to Open Science. Nevertheless, it is of great importance to Open Science in terms of transparency and verifiability, and it largely determines the extent to which a research project and its results can be open, open subject to conditions, or closed. That is why it has been included in OSI. • According to our information, at least five institutions are currently developing a system for this purpose. This leads to unnecessary fragmentation, whereas a joint system could accommodate institution-specific policies. • By ‘administrative platform’, we envisage a delegated/multi-tenant system that SURF could manage, thus providing each institution with its own ‘instance’. • The introduction of the RAiD project identifier is essential, as is the Grant ID for project funding. 	

Function: research administration/compliance with legislation and regulations	
<p>Federated solution(s)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative platform (multi-tenant setup) in which various components are available in an integrated manner (such as a data management plan tool, ethical review, DPIA) and which is linked per instance to the relevant administrative environments of the institution in question • Storage environment (institutional) for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Administrative data relating to research projects (thereby verifiable) ○ Also storage of data licences and responsibilities (who grants access, who is granted access), access conditions and who is responsible for deleting or retaining data for longer periods (data governance). 	<p>Agreement framework for the federation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction of RAiD identifier (Research Activity Identifier) • Agreements on metadata and data models (e.g. machine-actionable DMPs) • Support desk
<p>By connecting the federation modules</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instances of the multi-tenant system are automatically connected to one another 	
<p>Explanation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From an Open Science perspective, this highlights: (1) the importance of ‘carrying forward’ metadata generated during the various steps that is relevant for sharing, reuse and reproducibility, and (2) the automation of data access mechanisms, thereby supporting researchers in sharing datasets subject to specific conditions. 	

B1. INTRODUCTION

Section 1.2 sets out the scope of SPII Part 1 in bullet points. This appendix provides further explanation.

B2. DISTINGUISHING OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE FROM RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE:

SCOPE

The aim is to develop an infrastructure plan for Open Science and not for a digital research infrastructure (such as High Performance Computing, GWIs, etc.). In other words: OSI is the Open Science perspective on (digital) research infrastructure. This concerns the adjustments and additions required of the digital research infrastructure to facilitate Open Science. Alignment with the research infrastructures mentioned above is addressed in Part 2.

EXPLANATION

Research infrastructure comprises the digital resources required to conduct research, including laboratory equipment, High Performance Computing, tools, and the like. The focus is on supporting the research process and, in many cases, is directed towards discipline-specific research processes.

OSI can be seen as that functionality of the digital research infrastructure which is designed to make research and research results as open and reusable as possible, whilst the remaining functionality of the digital research infrastructure focuses on digital resources and services that support the other aspects of research – whether open or closed. OSI therefore involves modifications or additions to the research infrastructure that enable Open Science, with the ultimate goal being that all research infrastructure offers functionality that facilitates Open Science.

B3. FEDERATED INFRASTRUCTURE AS A STARTING POINT

SCOPE

- The starting point is to base SPII as much as possible on existing systems. That is why SPII proposes a federative/federation-like structure for OSI, built in a modular and integrated manner. A reference architecture for OSI (similar to HOSA) to be developed forms part of this structure.
- SPII Part 1 focuses on the technical design. The governance, organisation, resources and commitment required for a federative structure form part of the proposed SPII Part 2.

EXPLANATION

FEDERATED AND FEDERATION-LIKE MODELS

We can distinguish the following models that may be relevant to the Open Science infrastructure:

- **Centralised model:** All software, processes and controls are housed within a central body/server/service.
- **Aggregation model:** Data is periodically retrieved (aggregated) from various sources and merged into a central database or index.
- **Delegated model/multi-tenant model:** A shared software system is used by various institutions, but with their own configurations. Each ‘tenant’ of the system runs its own variant.
- **Federated model:** A network of autonomous parties collaborating on the basis of agreements and standards: there is no central storage or control, but mutual interoperability.

The aggregation model and the delegated/multi-tenant model can be regarded as ‘federation-like’. For the sake of clarity, the federation-like forms are also referred to as ‘federative’ in this report.

The table below illustrates some characteristics and examples of these models.

Infrastructure models	Centralised model	Federation-like	Federation-like	Federated model
		Delegated/multi-tenant model	Aggregation model	
Set-up	A single centralised system	One shared implementation with local ‘instances’	Multiple systems, metadata aggregated centrally	Different systems with common standards
Institution-specific data	Possible, but stored centrally	In separate instances	Stored locally and consolidated centrally	Fully managed locally
Autonomous policy possible	No	Partially independent	At source	Autonomous, subject to compliance with federal agreements
Examples	Traditional database, national register	CRIS system with local implementation such as PURE; DSpace Yoda, Dataverse.NL	OpenAIRE (via harvesting) Unpaywall (via crawling) ODISSEI portal	Federated identity management, EOSC

Table1 Comparison of digital infrastructure models

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE AND HORA/HOSA

The Higher Education Reference Architecture (HORA) and Higher Education Sector Architecture (HOSA) can be seen as an implementation of the Dutch Government Reference Architecture (NORA) for research and education.

HOSA is a sector architecture and has three translations into ‘domain architectures’: Education¹⁵, IAM¹⁶ and RDM¹⁷.

Digital education infrastructures are organised in a fairly centralised manner (compared to research infrastructure) and the HOSA domain architecture for education therefore describes a reasonably centralised, platform-oriented architecture, which is currently being implemented in stages. The HOSA domain architecture for IAM describes a transition from a more centralised architecture to a federated structure and envisages a further development towards a more decentralised structure.

Research infrastructures are fragmented and comprise both institution-specific and national components, as well as discipline-specific, often international components. A centralised research infrastructure consisting of one or a few platforms is therefore not on the agenda.

B4. RDSM, OSC AND ORI

SCOPE

SPII focuses on an OSI infrastructure for Research Data & Software Management, Open Scholarly Communication infrastructure and Open Research Information, and on the FAIR sharing of research results within these. SPII expects this to cover a significant part of the need for OSI.

EXPLANATION

The focus of SPII Part 1 is on Research Data & Software Management (RDSM), Open Scholarly Communication infrastructure (OSC) and Open Research Information (ORI) infrastructure. The aim is to support the creation, sharing and reuse of FAIR research data and software, Open Access publications and Open Access to other research outputs, such as tools, protocols, methods and open-source hardware, and to improve open research information about research at Dutch institutions.

With the focus on RDSM, OSC and ORI, the vast majority of the infrastructure for Open Science is covered. Infrastructure facilities for other components of Open Science, such as Citizen Science, can then be developed and linked at a later stage of OSI's development.

B5. DISCIPLINE-AGNOSTIC IN PART 1

SCOPE

SPII Part 1 focuses on OSI functionalities relevant to Dutch research projects regardless of their discipline. The initial focus is on data that institutions can and wish to share with one another in an effective and efficient manner through a federated infrastructure. The connection to more discipline-specific Open Science infrastructure components and to disciplinary research infrastructures will be addressed in Part 2.

EXPLANATION

Generic Open Science infrastructure components include generic modules such as general data repositories, software repositories, CRIS systems, institutional repositories, preprint servers, publication platforms, and persistent identifier systems (such as ORCID, DOI and ROR). In addition, there are Open Science infrastructure components that are more discipline-specific, such as domain-

specific data repositories, discipline-specific preprint servers and publication platforms, and open-source software tools for specific tasks such as the analysis of *genomic data* from laboratory experiments or software for astronomers.

APPENDIX C: STARTING POINTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE OSI REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE

C1. DERA AND THE NDE PROGRAMME AS AN EXAMPLE

The [Digital Heritage Network](#) programme has been in existence for 10 years and operates within a diverse landscape of heritage institutions. The core of the programme can be summarised as the interconnection of digital heritage. From the programme's inception, work has been carried out on a reference architecture – [DERA](#) – derived from the NORA reference architecture.

Work began with an initial version of DERA in which a number of principles were formulated. Over the course of the programme, DERA has been repeatedly expanded and updated. The respondent indicates that such a reference architecture has never been fully developed.

DERA acts as a kind of anchor and sometimes leads to the translation of requirements into concrete specifications for, for example, collection management systems. These are based on DERA and have also been drawn up in consultation with the suppliers of these systems (what is realistic and what is feasible). The results of this have in turn been incorporated into DERA. These requirements have now been accepted, and institutions can procure DERA-compliant collection management systems

DERA is therefore sometimes leading, but sometimes also follows developments in the field. These developments are monitored and discussed in periodic consultations on DERA and, where relevant, incorporated into a new version.

The conclusion is that DERA has had a guiding and harmonising effect on developments in the field of digital heritage. It acts as a beacon on the horizon, providing direction for what happens in practice. The respondent cites the scope of the reference architecture as the most important *lesson learnt*: it is essential to keep its objectives in mind at all times, so that its complexity does not become unnecessarily great.

C2. STARTING POINTS FOR THE OSI REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE

During the SPII Part 1 project, a number of starting points were derived from the various discussions, which are presented in tabular form on the following page. This table should be viewed as a bottom-up collection of observations, ideas and best practices that still require further discussion and refinement. Some key points from the table are:

- Make it easy for the researcher
- Create metadata at the source
- Develop an integrated metadata model for all forms of research information
- Support both conventional and innovative publication models
- Ensure an open approach in the development of OSI.

Principle	Sub-principle	Rationale	Consequences
Put the researcher experience front and centre	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make it easy and efficient to capture as much information as possible - create value for the researcher - Enter data only once 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish a national repository that accepts preprints, published articles, theses, reports and other documents. - Provide institutional access points to the repository. Allow relevant support staff to review submissions to ensure they are appropriate and properly described. Make metadata available via APIs and embed JSON-LD to ensure indexing. - Verify authors and their consent to publication, at a minimum via email and ORCID validation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make it easy for anyone affiliated with a member institution to submit a document. Support the entry of complete, high-quality metadata through automated extraction (potentially AI-based), autocompletion, database lookups and PID support. 	
Enable both conventional and innovative publication models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish a submission platform that supports configurable workflows for journal articles and books. - Integrate with the national repository, other repositories and preprint servers. - Consider a generic peer review platform that can be used for solicited or unsolicited reviews in any type of publication model. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Items to be reviewed can include publications, datasets and software. Promote open peer review and provide metadata about reviews. All reviewers must be authenticated. Allow other sites (e.g. repositories and journals) to pull in reviews and display them.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Centre publication workflows around the document. Instead of circulating files, leave the publication in place and add layers of annotations to it. - Support different versions of publications and allow for living, evolving documents. 		

Principle	Sub-principle	Rationale	Consequences
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Link publications to one another and to other outputs, such as datasets and software, as much as possible. - Integrate with an archive for the automatic preservation of items. 		
Collect research information throughout the research lifecycle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adopt a project-based approach to the research lifecycle to integrate administrative workflows and their associated metadata - Use RAiD as an identifier - Include data/software management plans, ethical reviews, GDPR documentation/information security classification, AI impact assessments, and other required documentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A great deal of information about research is generated along the way but is not captured and is only reconstructed afterwards - Reporting becomes much easier 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set up working groups with the relevant experts from institutions to harmonise these documents as much as possible and create machine-readable versions - Lobby NWO to use this metadata for reporting instead of manual entry in ISAAC
Curate metadata in source systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Start producing high-quality metadata at source instead of investing a lot of time in curating, merging and fixing data afterwards. - Carry out fewer data manipulations in the CRIS - Curate metadata about research outputs in the respective repositories - Aggregate metadata from source systems (such as repositories) and allow CRISs to subscribe to it. Do not aggregate metadata from CRISs, as it is not always clear where it originally comes from. - Expose all metadata so that it can be aggregated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information curated in downstream systems is difficult to extract, leading to duplication of effort and conflicting metadata - the provenance of metadata in non-source systems is not always clear 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish a system that allows institutions to model their internal organisation and to record researchers' affiliations. Allow institutions (and researchers) to claim an output for a specific person or organisational affiliation. Base reporting on this. 		

Principle	Sub-principle	Rationale	Consequences
An integrated, extensible, straightforward metadata model for all research information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use existing work as a basis, e.g. schema.org with JSON-LD serialisation - Promote the use of linked data across all systems. - Distinguish between entities (publications, persons, organisations, etc.) and records about them. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A linked data model allows for extension, missing information and connections between data sources - schema.org is widely adopted and provides a very rich vocabulary for research-specific metadata - This allows for explicit modelling of provenance, uncertainties in data quality, and integration of data sources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - create adapters for systems that do not yet use the integrated metadata model - Develop the metadata model entirely in the open on GitHub via pull requests and allow anyone to adopt it
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offer a cohesive data storage experience that makes it easy to move data into different storage solutions throughout the research lifecycle, and to a repository for publishing. - Enable automatic verification of stored data and software against the relevant data and software management plans. - Aggregate metadata for datasets and software and make it discoverable through search, recommendation and query interfaces. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enable collaboration on the data and the mounting of data sources in analysis environments.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consider using a single platform for collaborative software development. Integrate it with Software Heritage and the Research Software Directory. Make it easy to pull code from the platform into the analysis environments. 		
Develop Open Science infrastructure openly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discuss standards and software development publicly. - Encourage participation from anyone interested and adhering to a code of conduct. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open discussion that documents the thought process through which a decision was reached - Inclusive participation is a principle of Open Science and leads to solutions with broader support 	

Principle	Sub-principle	Rationale	Consequences
Benefit from work done in other communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Embrace the spirit of open-source development to build infrastructure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open-source practices are well established and have led to impressive outcomes - Learning, sharing and reuse are at the heart of Open Science 	

APPENDIX D: SUGGESTIONS FOR THE LAUNCH OF SPII PARTS 2 AND 3

INTRODUCTION

In the final days of the SPII Part 1 project, a number of comments and suggestions emerged that may be relevant to the proposed SPII Part 2 and Part 3 projects.

REVISITING THE SCOPE

A proposal has been received to work with a number of experts in the field of Citizen Science, using a number of use-cases in that field, to assess the extent to which the proposed OSI infrastructure meets the infrastructural needs of Citizen Science.

Furthermore, based on other comments, greater attention should be paid to digital collaboration environments in Part 2.

SPLITTING PART 2 AND PART 3

The risk of the proposed split is that the results of Part 2 would face a lack of organisation and funding to actually implement them. This is in light of a previous project on a potential Open Knowledge Base, in which many stakeholders invested a great deal of time but which nevertheless failed to get off the ground. Such a situation could potentially be mitigated by drawing up multiple scenarios regarding joint organisation and funding and discussing these at an administrative level at an earlier stage.

EXPLORATION OF POTENTIAL EXPANSION OF USE CASES

Several suggestions have been noted to expand the number of use cases and to assess whether this warrants adjustments to the federated diagrams and possibly modifications or additions to the OSI infrastructure. These suggestions include:

- Use cases relating to the implementation phase of research projects
- Use cases that integrate all domains
- Use cases from a research institute or research group
- Use cases from specific disciplines

ALIGNMENT WITH THE REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE AND CORE SERVICES OF EOSC AND NFDI

EOSC is developing a reference architecture and core services that enable access, interoperability and reliability. These include PID services, metadata registries (standards and vocabularies, FAIR sharing, RDA registries), monitoring and accounting (usage, availability, service performance) and *resource allocation*. The [NFDI](#) is also developing a reference architecture and has established, or is in the process of establishing, similar core services. SPII Part 2 would do well to study this reference architecture and core services and, where necessary, align them with the OSI proposals.

LOOKING AHEAD

SPII Part 1 was based on existing workflows. However, it is clear that technical developments are taking place, such as Artificial Intelligence and decentralisation, which could have a significant impact on the workflows of researchers and research support professionals and/or on the Open Science infrastructure. An exercise that takes these developments into account could potentially provide a longer-term outlook and make the deliverables of SPII Part 2 more future-proof.

INVENTORY OF RELEVANT ONGOING PROJECTS

It is recommended to identify which projects in the field of data infrastructures, data interoperability, publication platforms, etc. are currently underway, the results of which are expected to be relevant to OSI.

OTHER SUGGESTIONS

- **Reference architecture:** ‘Open by design/FAIR by design’ could also be included as a starting point. This involves making the underlying infrastructure FAIR.
- **Digilabs:** It is recommended to establish links with two Digilabs. The government’s [Digilab](#) is working on technical interoperability and the responsible sharing of data. In another [Digilab](#), five TO2 organisations and six national knowledge institutions are collaborating on the development of a federated digital infrastructure.
- **GORC model:** A great deal of thought has gone into the development of the [GORC model](#). The SPII Part 2 project may be able to make use of (some of) the results of this model.

APPENDIX E: PARTICIPANTS IN SPII PART 1

Steering Group	
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APPENDIX F: GLOSSARY

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
Data Access Broker	Acts as a 'broker' connecting researchers with providers of research datasets [enter a DOI; if open, direct access; if restricted access, redirect to the data provider's landing page].
Data transfer service	A data transfer service is a storage space where data are temporarily stored and processed before being moved to their final destination.
DataverseNL	DataverseNL is a research data repository managed by DANS, with separate instances managed by universities and universities of applied sciences.
DCC-IN	National implementation network of Digital Competence Centres (DCC-IN). The DCC-IN brings together IT departments and university libraries from all Dutch universities, university medical centres and KNAW and NWO institutes.
iRODS	iRODS is open-source data management software that offers a range of research data management (RDM) functionalities, such as secure data sharing, storage virtualisation, metadata management, access control and rule-based workflows. iRODS is fairly complex middleware that requires further configuration and integration before it can be used by researchers.
Dutch Research Portal	Aggregator of Dutch research information, based on OpenAire
Odissei	ODISSEI (Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations) is the national research infrastructure for the Dutch social sciences, comprising various components, including access to data, expertise and computing resources.
RAiD	Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) is a persistent identifier (PID) and global register for research projects. Regulated by ISO standard
RDX	Research Data Exchange: (1) a researcher makes a dataset available subject to conditions by answering a few questions; (2) a potential user wishes to access a dataset and digitally signs a contract by which they agree to those conditions. [So the Data Access Broker helps you gain access to the dataset, whilst RDX automates the process of restricted access].
SANE	Workspace for sensitive data (with 'compute to data')
SURF Research Cloud	SURF Research Cloud is a federated environment/portal where you can build a virtual research environment. You can use pre-configured workspaces and datasets or add your own. Benefits: (1) creating reproducible research environments; (2) utilising the best facilities; and (3) collaborating securely. Computing and storage are provided.
TDCC	Thematic Digital Competence Centres: Life Science & Health (LSH); Natural and Engineering Sciences (NES); Social and Human Sciences (SSH)
URN:NBN resolver	The Uniform Resource Name (URN) is a Persistent Identifier (PID) which – unlike URLs – allows online resources to be uniquely and permanently identified, regardless of where they are stored. nbn: National Bibliographic Number

YODA	<p>YODA is an application for institutions that supports RDM throughout the entire research cycle: from the secure and simple storage and sharing of data during the research process, to the sharing of data within research groups and projects, and ultimately to the archiving and publication of research data. YODA uses iRODS as its underlying technology.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• User-friendly (web-based, graphical user interface and the WebDAV interface)• Supports the entire research process from data acquisition to publication• Supports standardised workflows for the storage and archiving of research data• Direct link between data and metadata (including flexible metadata schemas)• Data publication and the associated generation of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)• Flexible integration with iRODS that is also suitable for (highly) data-intensive research.
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